

22IEM05 NEWSTAND

D5: Report on the interlaboratory comparisons of the newly developed transfer standard light sources, the detector-based transfer standards for spectral irradiance in the UV-VIS-NIR spectral ranges and the associated methods

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22IEM05 NEWSTAND

April 1, 2026

A3.1.1 Report on the interlaboratory comparison of the newly developed broadband transfer standard UV sources

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Contents

Disclaimer	3
1. Introduction and scope	4
2. Type of comparison	4
3. Measurand	4
4. Instruments and participants	4
4.1. Participating spectroradiometers	4
4.2. Monitor spectroradiometer	5
4.3. Reference measurements	5
5. Description of the transfer standards	5
5.1. Broadband UV-LED source by Aalto	5
5.1.1. Design	5
5.1.2. Specifications	6
5.1.3. Nominal operating conditions	7
5.2. Broadband UV-LED source by TÜBITAK	8
5.2.1. Design	8
5.2.2. Specifications	8
5.2.3. Nominal operating conditions	9
6. Results	10
6.1. Aalto-UV source by Aalto	10
6.1.1. Spectral irradiance	10
6.1.2. Reproducibility	11
6.1.3. Intercomparison	12
6.2. CALIS-UV source by TÜBITAK	13
6.2.1. Spectral irradiance	13
6.2.2. Reproducibility	14
6.2.3. Intercomparison	15
7. Conclusions	16
Acknowledgments	17

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1. Introduction and scope

This report summarizes the results of an interlaboratory comparison arranged as activity A3.1.1 in project NEWSTAND. According to the project protocol, at least one of the broadband transfer standard UV light sources developed in A1.2.1 was to be measured, with the aim of verifying the uncertainties that can be achieved at calibration laboratory level [as low as 0.5 % ($k = 2$)]. Two sources, one developed by Aalto and one by TUBITAK were included in the measurements.

2. Type of comparison

The original plan was to circulate the sources among participants. However, during the project, this appeared unfeasible due to fragility and complexity of the sources. Thus, the sources were brought to PTB Braunschweig, and the participants brought their spectroradiometers there. The measurements were carried out between 20 and 24 October 2025.

3. Measurand

The measurand was spectral irradiance in [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$]. All spectroradiometers were aligned to the same reference distance from the source. These distances were measured in the beginning, and during the measurements they were set mechanically.

4. Instruments and participants

Two UV sources were measured: CALIS-UV developed by TUBITAK, and Aalto-UV developed by Aalto University.

4.1. Participating spectroradiometers

The participants, their instruments participating, and their key characteristics are listed in **Table 1**. All devices were array spectroradiometers, except PTB-ref, that was used as the reference instrument. Most devices measured over a larger wavelength range than that covered by the UV sources, extending up to the visible and near-infrared regions. For CALIS-UV, the results were analysed for the spectral range 250 nm – 500 nm while for Aalto-UV over 230 nm – 500 nm, where the sources provided well measurable signals. A more detailed description of the spectroradiometers can be found in “A3.1.4 Report on the measurement intercomparison of the transfer standard array spectroradiometers.”

Table 1. Instruments participating in the UV comparison.

Participant	Spectroradiometer Name	Label	Spectral Range / nm	No. of Pixels	Spectral Band-width / nm	Pixel spacing /nm/pixel	Entrance Optics diameter/mm
PTB	CAS-140D UV-VIS	sp08	200 - 830	1024x128	3	0.8	15
GGO	BTS2048-UVVISNIR	sp13	200 - 900	2048	2	0.34	10
VSL	AvaSpec-VRS2048CL-EVO	sp35	190 - 1100	2048	2.44	0.46	10

Aalto	CAS 140D	sp37	219 - 1029	1024x128	3.7	0.8	10
VSL	AvaSpec-VRS2048CL-EVO	sp47	190 - 1100	2048	1.88	0.46	10
PTB	BTS2048-UVVISNIR	sp49	200 - 900	2048	2	0.34	10
PTB	BTS2048-UV	sp51	200 - 430	2048	0.8	0.13	10
GGO	BTS2048-UV	sp79	200 - 430	2048	0.8	0.13	10
PTB	Spectro320D*	ref	190 - 1600	n/a	1 (2)		15

*) Scanning double-monochromator spectroradiometer used as reference instrument

4.2. Monitor spectroradiometer

During the measurement campaign, all UV sources were additionally measured using a monitor spectroradiometer, a BTS2048 array spectroradiometer with a spectral bandwidth of 0.8 nm and spectral range 200 nm - 430 nm. It was placed in front of the sources shortly after the start and at the end of each measurement session for comparison purposes, in order to verify stability and reproducibility. Due to its available spectral range, the array spectroradiometer measures only partially the spectral range of the sources, but it provides sufficient indication of the stability and reproducibility of the irradiance levels.

4.3. Reference measurements

For reference measurements of the spectral irradiance, a Spectro320D double monochromator-based fast scanning spectroradiometer was used. As a double monochromator system, it provides superior stray light suppression and features a symmetrical nearly triangular bandpass function that is constant throughout the spectral range. The spectral range between 250 nm and 885 nm wavelengths was measured with 1 nm bandwidth using a photomultiplier tube. The entrance optics for the spectroradiometer include a transmissive diffusor (EOP146) with good cosine correction and medium throughput for the spectral range 190 nm – 2500 nm. Due to the transmission characteristics of the input optics, particularly in measurements below 300 nm, relatively high standard deviations were observed. This resulted in higher measurement uncertainties in some cases, as well as deviations in the comparison measurements.

5. Description of the transfer standards

5.1. Broadband UV-LED source by Aalto

5.1.1. Design

Aalto-UV depicted in Figure 1 has been designed for wavelength region 250 nm – 450 nm. The source consists of a UVC LED matrix emitting radiation at the wavelength of 277 nm, and a UVA + UVB phosphor disk that absorbs part of the LED radiation and re-emits it at longer wavelengths covering UV-A and UV-B regions. The LED matrix is attached to an air-cooled heatsink to get rid of the excess heat. A UV coated Ø75 mm plano-convex lens has been added to the design to collect intensity. Further information on the source is given in [1].

Figure 1. Aalto-UV light source.

5.1.2. Specifications

Figure 2 presents the optical arrangement of the source built inside an optical tube. Distance between the LED matrix and the phosphor disk is $d_{\text{Phos}} = 22.9$ mm. Distance between the phosphor disk and the lens is $d_{\text{Lens}} = 64.0$ mm. The distance from the lens to the outermost surface of the tube is $d_{\text{Cap}} = 47.3$ mm.

The reference plane for distance measurements is the outermost surface of the tube with its protecting cap closed. Measurement distance from this reference plane is $d_{\text{Meas}} = 500.0$ mm.

Figure 2. Optical arrangement of the Aalto-UV source. For dimensions, see text.

The LED matrix is operated with current of 1.000 A. Leads have banana plugs. The voltage across the lamp rises up to 17.3 V.

The fan is operated with a voltage source providing 5 V via banana plugs. Inside the heat sink, there is a 10 k Ω NTC thermistor that is read with a multimeter. There is an adapter providing banana plugs for connection.

The intensity of the lamp decays gradually. Intensity integrated over the LED peak region, 250 nm – 295 nm drops by 0.03 %/h. Corresponding decay in the phosphor region, integrated over 296 nm – 450 nm wavelength range is 0.11 %/h.

The spatial uniformity is somewhat limited due to using the lens. If the diameters of the entrance optics of the measurement instruments deviate a lot from each other, the resulting effect can be corrected using data of Figure 3.

Figure 3. Irradiance masked through different sizes of measurement apertures.

5.1.3. Nominal operating conditions

Environment - The light source has been designed and tested to be used in ordinary laboratory conditions, temperature preferably 23 °C.

Fan cooling - The LED matrix generates about 17 W of power. With the fan on, the temperature of the heat sink and the LED matrix rises to 29 °C, 6 °C above the environmental temperature. Without fan (not recommended) the temperature rises to above 35 °C. The fan is operated with a 5 V power supply.

Electrical parameters - The LED matrix is operated with 1.000 A DC current. Voltage over the lamp is monitored and compared to earlier values. The voltage level is approximately 17.3 V.

Alignment and reference plane - The measuring device should be positioned 500.0 mm from the reference plane (front plate), on an optical axis defined by a mirror placed in contact with the front plate and a laser reflected from the mirror, and the center of the front plate marked with an X.

Temporal stability - A warm-up time of 1 h should be allowed. The intensity gradually decays. Thus, a record is kept on the lamp burn hours, including voltage across the lamp in the beginning and at the end.

5.2. Broadband UV-LED source by TÜBITAK

5.2.1. Design

CALIS-UV is a tuneable broadband UV LED source, designed and established having 250 nm – 405 nm wavelength range and irradiance higher than 1 mW/m² at each wavelength. The source consists of 79 LEDs, arranged in fourteen spectral groups, each group containing LEDs with a different peak wavelength. The LEDs are positioned on a circular PCB in the configuration shown in Figure 4 in order to achieve uniform irradiation.

Figure 4. Left: Schematic layout of the 79 UV LEDs, illustrating the placement and wavelength classification of the LEDs within the circular PCB. Right: Picture of the LEDs on the PCB.

A multi-channel current driver is used to provide current to the 14 LED groups. Each current channel can be set individually for need of the specific LED group. The multi-channel current driver gives flexibility and opportunities for having different spectral power distributions. The multi-channel current driver is powered by an external DC power supply. The current control is performed by “UV LED PROGRAM V1.065” software.

For temperature stability of the LEDs, the LED PCB is mounted on a Thermoelectric Cooler, Arroyo Instruments 286-C0866 TECMount, which was custom-manufactured based on the LED PCB size and the expected thermal load. Further information on the source is given in [1].

5.2.2. Specifications

The dimensional drawings of the customized cold plate of the TEC are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Drawing of the cold plate of the TEC (lengths in mm).

The spectrum given in Figure 6 shows multiple low-intensity peaks in the 260–350 nm region, representing the combined emission of several UV LED groups with closely spaced wavelengths. The two strong maxima around ~365 nm and ~395 nm indicate that the LED types at these wavelengths contribute the dominant radiant power. The low-intensity peaks in the 260 nm – 350 nm region, where the smallest peaks are below approximately $0.03 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{nm}^{-1}$. The two dominant emission bands occur near ~365 nm and ~395 nm, with the maximum peak reaching about $0.27 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{nm}^{-1}$.

Figure 6. Spectral irradiance of the CALIS-UV source at a distance of 500 mm.

The source exhibits very stable spectral output over the UV region after the initial warm-up period. In the 250 nm – 300 nm region, the stability after 30 minutes remains within $\pm 1\%$, while in the 300 nm – 405 nm range the variation is further reduced to below $\pm 0.5\%$. After one hour of operation, the stability curve shows an additional improvement, indicating that the system reaches a steady thermal and electrical equilibrium.

5.2.3. Nominal operating conditions

Environment - Conditions with ambient temperature between 20 °C and 30 °C and relative humidity between 30 % and 70 % are recommended.

Thermoelectric cooling - Since the large number of LEDs generates a significant thermal load on the 10-cm-diameter PCB, temperature monitoring is performed, not only via the temperature sensor located behind the TEC cold plate, but also by an additional sensor placed at the center of the PCB. Because the target temperature on the PCB is 25 °C, the LED board can be maintained at this level when the TEC is fixed at 18 °C. To ensure stable source irradiance, the TEC temperature must remain constant at 18 °C so that the PCB temperature, as monitored by the onboard sensor, stays close to 25 °C.

Electrical parameters - The source must be switched on only when the TEC is active. The external DC power supply must provide 12 V and 15 A to drive the multi-channel current driver. Using the user interface software, the operator must set the driving current for the LEDs across 14 channels, ensuring that the current for each channel remains below the maximum value indicated as “MAX:” in the interface.

Alignment and reference plane - The sensor should be positioned such that its center aligns with the center of the PCB. A distance of 500 mm is recommended for the measurements.

Spatial homogeneity - The physical configuration, where multiple LEDs of various wavelengths are positioned within a 10 cm circular PCB results in a broad area of emission. Consequently, the spatial homogeneity cannot be expected to be as ideal as that of a point source. The measurements have been conducted to characterize this parameter and calculated 1.2 % a 6 cm x 7 cm area centered around the optical axis at 500 mm distance from the source.

Temporal stability - A warm-up time of 1 h should be allowed.

6. Results

6.1. Aalto-UV source by Aalto

6.1.1. Spectral irradiance

Measurement results of the participants on the Aalto-UV source are presented in Figure 7. For comparison, there is also the spectral irradiance of a 150-W incandescent lamps shown. The spectral irradiance consists of the peak of the excitation LED at 277 nm, with two other peaks at longer wavelengths and a long-wavelength tail from the phosphor disk. In the short-wavelength spectral region, the spectral irradiance is significantly higher than, e.g., the spectral irradiance of the 150-W halogen incandescent lamp at a distance of 300 mm shown. The irradiance of Aalto-UV is comparable to that of a 1000 W tungsten halogen lamp at 500 mm distance. The three peaks in the spectrum of the source require the array spectroradiometers to have very good wavelength assignment and sufficiently good bandwidth correction.

Figure 7. Spectral irradiance of the Aalto-UV source measured by several array spectrometers. The dashed line shows the spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp at 300 mm distance.

6.1.2. Reproducibility

During the comparison, the radiation source was operated on three consecutive days and measured each day with the monitor spectrometer. These measurements demonstrate the reproducibility of the source. Figure 8 shows the reproducibility of the radiation source compared to Day 1 (solid purple line at zero). On Day 2 (lower light blue lines), there are hardly any changes to report. This yields a spectrally independent correction factor of 1.0018. The changes on Day 3 (red lines) are slightly larger, possibly due to minor changes in thermal conditions, resulting in a correction factor of 0.9911.

Measurements at different days, were corrected using the average correction factors. If preferred, they could also be corrected spectrally, but this was not deemed necessary.

Figure 8. Relative spectral change of the Aalto-UV source at different days as indicated by the monitor spectroradiometer. The dotted lines indicate the spectrally independent average changes in the longer wavelength region, used for corrections. For explanation of the line colors, see text.

6.1.3. Intercomparison

The deviations between the spectral irradiance values reported by the array spectroradiometers and the results from the reference spectroradiometer are shown in Figure 9. The reference spectrum is also shown for illustrative purposes (right y-axis). The dotted lines represent the combined relative expanded measurement uncertainties for each individual array spectroradiometer and the reference spectroradiometer. For the comparison, the instruments were recalibrated on-site against the 150-W halogen incandescent lamp at a distance of 300 mm, and the daily corrections for the monitor spectroradiometer were taken into account. Good agreement between the spectroradiometers can be observed across wide spectral ranges. Only in the spectral regions with steeper slopes, there are larger deviations sometimes visible, which are likely due to a lack of bandpass correction. However, two spectrometers, sp35 and sp47, deviate substantially more from the others. Also sp13 deviates in the 300 – 340 nm region. These deviations are not due to the radiation source, but rather to insufficient characterization of the instruments. It is noteworthy that all spectroradiometers measure low above

430 nm, and most spectrometers measure low below 300 nm. These are the regions with low spectral irradiance values.

Figure 9. Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of the Aalto-UV source by several array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

6.2. CALIS-UV source by TÜBITAK

6.2.1. Spectral irradiance

Measurements of the participants on the CALIS-UV source are presented in Figure 10. The spectral irradiance consists of the spectra of multiple narrow-band LEDs. For direct comparison, the spectrum of a 150-W tungsten halogen lamp, measured at a distance of 300 mm, is also shown. The spectral irradiance of the CALIS-UV source exceeds that of a 1000-W tungsten halogen lamp at 500 mm distance. This UV source thus achieved a considerably high spectral irradiance, particularly in the UV-A spectral range. However, as with other LED sources, the peaks place special demands on array spectroradiometers in terms of wavelength assignment and spectral bandwidth correction.

Figure 10. Spectral irradiance of the CALIS-UV source measured by several array spectrometers. The dashed line shows the spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp at 300 mm distance.

6.2.2. Reproducibility

During the comparison, the radiation source was operated on three consecutive days and measured each day with the monitor spectrometer. These measurements demonstrate the reproducibility of the source. Figure 11 shows the reproducibility of the radiation source compared to Day 1 (solid purple line at zero). The noticeable deviations in the short-wavelength spectral range below 235 nm on the following measurement days (blue lines for Day 2 and red for Day 3) suggest that the settings for the short-wavelength LEDs may have been slightly different. A spectral correction of the reference measurement was performed here. For the spectral range above 325 nm, however, a spectrally

independent correction of 0.9962 for Day 2 (light blue middle curve) and 0.9955 for Day 3 (upper red curve) was sufficient.

Figure 11. Relative spectral change of the CALIS-UV source at different days as indicated by the monitor spectroradiometer. The dotted lines indicate the spectral independent changes in the longer wavelength region. For colors of the lines, see text.

6.2.3. Intercomparison

The deviations between the spectral irradiance values reported by the array spectroradiometers and the results from the reference spectroradiometer are shown in Figure 12. The reference spectrum is also shown for illustrative purposes (right y-axis). The dotted lines represent the combined relative expanded measurement uncertainties for each individual array spectroradiometer and the reference spectroradiometer. For the comparison, the instruments were recalibrated on-site against the 150 W halogen incandescent lamp at a distance of 300 mm, and the corrections for the monitor spectroradiometer were taken into account. Good agreement between the spectroradiometers can be observed across wide spectral ranges. Only in spectral regions with steeper slopes, we can see larger deviations, which are likely due to a lack of bandpass correction. As with the Aalto-UV source, two spectrometers, sp35 and sp47, deviate substantially more from the others, and sp13 deviates in the 300 – 340 nm region. These deviations are not due to the radiation source, but rather to insufficient characterization of the instruments. Most spectroradiometers measure low above 450 nm.

Figure 12. Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of the CALIS-UV source by several array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

7. Conclusions

Two newly developed broadband UV sources, Aalto-UV and CALIS-UV, were measured during a measurement intercomparison campaign at PTB by eight array spectroradiometers of the consortium partners and a scanning double-monochromator spectroradiometer. The stability and reproducibility of the sources were evaluated for the time of the comparison using a monitor spectroradiometer.

Aalto-UV appeared very stable in the campaign. Deviation between Days 1 and 2 was on the average 0.18 %. Wavelength dependence was minimal. For Day 3, the spectral irradiance raised by 0.89 %, which could be an environmental or alignment issue rather than a property of the source as its spectral irradiance is more likely to decrease.

The CALIS-UV source was very stable above 325 nm wavelengths. Change for Day 2 was 0.38 % and for Day 2, it was 0.45 %. Below 325 nm, there were spectral changes within 2.5 – 5 %, indicating that the LEDs providing low wavelengths had an issue with their currents.

Comparing results obtained with Aalto-UV and CALIS-UV with each other reveals a significant finding. Shapes of all deviations are similar with both sources. This indicates that indeed they may be used as transfer standards, However, the measuring instruments have to be carefully characterised to measure correctly in the wavelength regions with steep changes and low irradiance values. The best characterised instruments measured the Aalto-UV source with an agreement of 1 % and the CALIS-UV source with an agreement of 2 % in the mid-UV range having suitable irradiance levels.

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¹ P. Kärh, . Yaran, Z. Alpaslan Ksemen, O. Kuittinen, A. Eghbali, *Use of the prototype sources for the ultraviolet spectral range*, Good Practice Guide developed in project Newstand, 15 p. (2025).

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A3.1.2 Results and Technical Protocol for the interlaboratory comparison of the VIS LED transfer standard LIS-A²

Use of the transfer standard light sources developed in
A1.2.2 for the VIS spectral range

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Contents

Disclaimer	3
1. Description of activity A3.1.2	4
2. Introduction	4
3. Participants	4
4. Type of comparison	4
5. Description of the artefacts	5
5.1. Design description	5
5.2. Temperature stabilisation	8
5.3. Transfer standard light source: LIS-A ²	9
6. Transportation and use of the LIS-A ² artefacts	12
6.1. Transportation	12
6.2. Safety instructions	12
6.3. Assembly and alignment instructions	13
6.4. Operating LIS-A ²	19
7. Use of the PTB halogen incandescent lamp	22
8. Results	23
8.1. Ageing effects	23
8.2. Electrical properties	24
8.3. Results of PTB (Pilot)	25
8.4. Results of ISFH	27
8.5. Results of CSIC	31
8.6. Results of Le Cnam	36
8.7. Results of GGO	41
8.8. Results of AALTO	45
8.9. Overview of results of LIS-A ² LED#1	49
8.10. Overview of results of LIS-A ² LED#2	50
8.11. Overview of results of LIS-A ² LED#3	51
9. Appendix A – Artefact condition upon arrival	52
10. Appendix B – Artefact condition upon departure	53
11. Appendix C – Table of results	54
Acknowledgments	55

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1. Description of activity A3.1.2

“PTB will organise an interlaboratory comparison for at least 1 of the broadband transfer standard light sources for the VIS spectral range that was developed in A1.2.2 with the aim of verifying the uncertainties that can be achieved at calibration laboratory level (as low as 0.5 % ($k = 2$)). At least 1 of the new broadband transfer standard light sources from A1.2.2 will be measured using the calibration facilities of the NMI participants (PTB, CSIC, Le Cnam, NPL) and the calibration laboratories (GGO, IS, ISFH).

For comparison, PTB will provide a conventional FEL-lamp transfer standard for measurement by the participants in the interlaboratory comparison. A summary report will be written.”

2. Introduction

The aim of the comparison is to assess the quality and robustness of the VIS-LED spectral irradiance standard developed in the work package 1 of the project, and to study the measurement uncertainties that can be reached using highly characterized spectroradiometers at calibration laboratory level.

3. Participants

Table 1 lists the participants of the comparison to measure the spectral irradiance of different sources. PTB acts as the pilot, thus collecting the data of the partners and preparing the comparison report.

Table 1 List of participants and the devices used in the measurements.

Participant	Array Spectroradiometer	Double Monochromator
PTB (pilot)	x	x
ISFH	x	
CSIC	x	
Le Cnam		x
GGO	x	
Aalto	x	
PTB (pilot)	x	x

4. Type of comparison

PTB provides four lamps. Three of them are LIS-A² LED sources which were designed and manufactured within the scope of activity A1.2.2. In addition, a halogen incandescent lamp (PTB-KSL-104; 6 amperes, approx. 21 volts) is included so that systematic errors between LED and incandescent lamp measurements can be identified. After seasoning and accessing the quality of the lamps, PTB will measure the spectral irradiance of all four sources according to the measurement procedure of this protocol before transporting the artefacts to the next partners. After each partner has carried out their own measurements of all lamps, the artefacts are transported to the next partner in

the measurement order. Finally, PTB will re-measure all four sources. The measurement order is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Order of the comparison measurements.

5. Description of the artefacts

5.1. Design description

The design of the LIS-A light source from the EURAMET European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) project 15SIB07 PhotoLED (<http://photoled.aalto.fi/>) was successful and serves as the basis for the development of the broadband VIS source.

Figure 2 LIS-A reference light source.

The housing includes high-quality temperature stabilisation and a proven and good arrangement of individual LEDs. As the new source requires several different LED types to be operated at different currents, the housing and circuit design have been adapted. In addition, a laser was built into the housing to align the source, which shines through the LED board and specifies the direction in which the coupling optics of the spectroradiometer should be attached.

The result is a source which we call LIS-A² and which is shown and described in the following images.

Figure 3 The left rendered image shows the LIS-A² source. The marked laser beam indicates the measurement direction. The right image shows the real prototype during the NEWSTAND measurement campaign at the PTB.

Figure 4 Front view of the LIS-A² with dimensions in millimetres.

Figure 5 Side view of the LIS-A² with dimensions in millimetres.

Figure 6 Bottom side view. An optical post or tripod can be attached to the bottom of the LIS-A² standard light source. There is one M6 tapped hole and one 1/4" tapped hole at the base. There are two additional bores with H7 tolerance. The bottom side should be aligned perpendicular to gravity.

5.2. Temperature stabilisation

LEDs used as transfer standard lamp should be operated on a temperature-stabilized heatsink when used as references because temperature significantly impacts their optical parameters.

The emitted flux and spectral characteristics of LEDs vary with temperature, typically decreasing optical power as temperature rises due to mechanisms such as non-radiative recombination and carrier leakage. Stabilizing the temperature ensures more consistent light output and colour stability, which is crucial for reliable measurements and calibration. Without temperature control, variations of ambient temperature affect the thermal equilibrium and lead to fluctuations in light output and peak wavelengths, reducing the stability and accuracy of the LED as a reference source.

Using a temperature-stabilized heatsink minimizes these temperature-induced variations, enhancing the precision and repeatability of optical referencing with LEDs. The used sourcemeters and the temperature stabilisation should be connected to the mains for at least 2 hours. The LEDs of the LIS-A² light source can then be switched on and measurements can be taken after a warm-up time of around 5 minutes.

Figure 7 This is a separate enclosure designed to interface with the LIS-A² light source. On the front panel, there are connectors for powering three independent LED circuits, each labeled with its respective current and voltage ratings. A toggle switch activates the built-in alignment laser. A green indicator LED in the right image shows that the source has reached thermal equilibrium.

5.3. Transfer standard light source: LIS-A²

For the measurement campaign at PTB and for comparison measurements between different laboratories, three LIS-A² standard lamps were built.

Figure 8 Three LIS-A² artifacts with and without protective caps.

The images in Figure 8 show three LIS-A² standard lamps arranged vertically. In the left panel, each lamp is fitted with a protective cap covering the emission aperture to shield the front glass and LED array and prevent contamination or mechanical damage during storage and transport. In the right panel, these caps have been removed, revealing the circular LED boards with the ring of broadband Yujileds and the central UV LEDs inside each housing. The consistent mechanical design and interchangeable front caps support reproducible positioning and handling in calibration setups, while the robust enclosures provide thermal and mechanical stability for the light sources.

Figure 9 LED arrangement and central LASER beam for alignment.

Each lamp contains an LED board with ten Yujiled CIE-E LEDs arranged in a circular ring and an additional set of five UV LEDs with peak wavelengths of 365 nm, 375 nm, 385 nm, 395 nm, and 405 nm mounted inside the ring.

Figure 10 Full LIS-A² setup.

Figure 10 shows a single standard LIS-A² lamp and its associated power sources. The LIS-A² is mounted on an adjustable post on the optical table, while three stacked SourceMeter units on the right provide precisely controlled currents for the different LED strings. The LED drive currents are set to very low levels to avoid saturating the camera image, so that the individual emitters are clearly visible. The inner ring of the LED array shows the different coloured UV LEDs, surrounded by the brighter broadband Yujileds which form the outer ring and dominate the visible output.

Every board is divided into three independent current circuits. Since connecting all ten broadband LEDs in series would require an impractically high supply voltage of about 180 V, they are split into two separate strings of five identical LEDs, each operated at 200 mA. A third circuit supplies the five UV LEDs. The drive current of the UV channel is adjusted so that, in combination with the broadband Yujileds, the resulting composite spectrum exhibits an almost constant spectral irradiance over the entire visible range as shown in Figure 11. This electrical architecture allows precise, reproducible control of the spectral power distribution while keeping the operating voltages within a safe and convenient range.

Figure 11 Relative spectral irradiance of a LIS-A² artifact.

Because the UV LEDs inside the LIS-A² could not be arranged in a perfectly rotationally symmetric pattern, the irradiance uniformity had to be verified at different distances from the source. The following figures show the relative spectral irradiance over the wavelength range from 340 nm to 800 nm for two distances. The blue circle marks a field with a diameter of 11.3 mm, corresponding to the typical entrance optics of spectroradiometers according to CIE report 127:2007 (Measurement of LEDs), while the black circle indicates a 20 mm diameter, which covers the vast majority of practical detector apertures.

Since typical measurement distances lie between 350 mm and 700 mm, the irradiance distribution was characterized for both distances. In both cases, the color maps demonstrate that within the blue and black circles the relative deviations from the central irradiance level are very small, indicating a highly uniform illumination of the detector aperture. For intermediate distances, which will be used in real measurement setups, the field can be expected to be at least as uniform, so the LIS-A² geometry is well suited for accurate spectroradiometer calibration without introducing significant spatial non-uniformity errors.

Figure 12 VIS irradiance uniformity at a distance of 350 mm.

Figure 13 VIS irradiance uniformity at a distance of 700 mm.

6. Transportation and use of the LIS-A² artefacts

6.1. Transportation

The artefacts were sent by the PTB in robust packaging with a strong outer shell and lots of soft material inside. The LED modules must be protected with their sealing cap during transport!

Upon receiving the shipment, the person in charge should inspect the contents as soon as possible for potential damage. If the artefact passes the visual inspection, it will be used according to the usage instructions to see that it is working properly. The participant will fill out a short inspection report and confirmation of receipt, see Appendices, and send it to the pilot laboratory. If deviations from the expected behavior occur during the measurements, they should be reported to the pilot and any other relevant participants (e.g., the next participant in the measurement chain).

6.2. Safety instructions

To prevent the source from damage, the following handling instructions must be respected:

- Avoid looking directly into the light output area, especially at close distances, as the intense visible and UV radiation may cause eye strain or damage!
- Use appropriate eye protection when working near the lamp without beam enclosures.
- Ensure that all personnel working with the LIS-A² are trained in its operation and familiar with general LED and UV safety guidelines, including applicable photobiological safety standards.

- The source is meant for operation in laboratory conditions and should not be used in other environments.
- Only operate the power sources with 230 volts and 50 hertz mains voltage!
- Operate the LIS-A² lamp only with the specified power supplies and wiring; do not modify the electrical connections or exceed the rated currents and voltages.
- Ensure that the protective front cap is mounted whenever the lamp is not in use or is being transported, to prevent mechanical damage and contamination of the optics.
- Allow sufficient ventilation around the housing and do not cover cooling openings; operate the lamp only within the specified ambient temperature range between +20°C and +30°C.
- Switch off the lamp before moving, performing any mechanical adjustments, cleaning, or reconfiguration of the setup.
- Current to the LEDs must not be applied when the TEC is inactive.
- No reverse bias should be applied to the LEDs.
- The source must not be exposed to liquids, moisture, dust or flames. Use only dry, lint-free materials and suitable cleaning agents for the front window; never use aggressive solvents on optical or plastic parts.

6.3. Assembly and alignment instructions

1. Place the three Keithley sourcemeter on top of each other.

2. Connect the black power cables to the back.

3. Connect the lower sourcemeter to the middle sourcemeter with a GPIB cable and screw them tight by hand.

4. Connect the middle Sourcemeater to the top Sourcemeater with a GPIB cable and screw them tight by hand.
5. Connect one of the Sourcemeters to the blue GPIB-USB-adapter and screw it tight.

6. Connect the USB cable of the blue GPIB-USB-adapter to the notebook (not shown on the following picture).
7. Connect the plug-in power supply unit to the notebook

8. Connect the three silver LEMO plugs coming from the green Phoenix plugs on the back of the sourcemeter to the silver TEC controller according to their labelling (Plug LED #1 connector to LED #1 socket)

9. Connect the grey Sub-D cable to the TEC controller and the LIS-A² source.

10. Connect the plug-in power supply unit to the mains, **but do not yet connect it to the TEC controller!**

11. Attach an optical post or tripod to the bottom of the LIS-A² standard light source. There is one M6 tapped hole and one 1/4" tapped hole at the base. There are two additional bores with H7 tolerance. The bottom side should be aligned perpendicular to gravity.

12. Remove the dust protection cap.

13. Connect the plug-in power supply unit to the TEC controller. The fan starts to work.

14. Switch on the laser from the front of the TEC controller. Do not look directly into the laser beam!

15. Place the centre of your spectroradiometer entrance optics in the laser beam.

16. Turn off the Laser.

17. Screw the Thorlabs alignment cap onto the LIS-A².

18. Adjust the distance between the front of the Thorlabs alignment cap and the reference plane of your spectroradiometer entrance optics to 500mm.
19. Repeat the alignment steps until you are satisfied.
20. Power on the Notebook and start the LIS-A² software in the centre of the desktop with a double click.

6.4. Operating LIS-A²

If necessary, run the software with the upper left arrow

Be sure that the plug-in power supply is connected to the TEC controller.

Push the Button “LED Switch”

Select the connected LED module. The name of the LED module can be found on the front of the LIS-A².

After that the LIS-A² will be turned on. The software gives you all relevant information, including the voltage of each electrical circuit.

LIS-A² Status

NOT STABLE

LED Switch

LED ON

Active LED#

3

Switch-on time

08:07:01.532
15.12.2025

Operating time

4.0 minutes

Keithley A initialized?

Communication Error Keithley A

Status	Code
✓	d0
Quelle	

Voltage left LED half ring

Keithley B initialized?

Communication Error Keithley B

Status	Code
✓	d0
Quelle	

Voltage inner LED ring

Keithley C initialized?

Communication Error Keithley C

Status	Code
✓	d0
Quelle	

Voltage right LED half ring

After a couple of minutes, the LIS-A² will reach a stable operating state. This is indicated in the software by the status. This appears in green and is labelled STABLE.

Carry out the spectral measurements.

When you have finished your measurements, note the burning time and voltage indication in Appendix C.

Push the LED Switch in the software to turn the LIS-A² off.

Disconnect the plug-in power supply unit to the TEC controller. The fan stops to work.

Put the dust protection cap on the LIS-A² standard light source.

Some errors are recognised by the software and the solution is then suggested by an instruction on the screen.

If you still encounter problems, please contact thorsten.gerloff@ptb.de or call +49 531 592 4128.

7. Use of the PTB halogen incandescent lamp

Reference plane for PTB-KSL-104:
front surface alignment-aid/ crosshairs

Measurement distance: (300 mm)

Power supply unit for PTB-KSL-104:

The power supply unit should be set to 6.00 A.
Check by pressing the "Prev" button:

deactivate the "Prev" button after testing:

When 6.00 A is set, turn the "Voltage" knob to power up the lamp.

Turn the voltage slightly higher. The current is limited.

The voltage should be around 20 V - 21 V.

After switching on the lamp, wait 15 minutes before starting measurements so that a stable thermal equilibrium can be established.

Note the burning time and voltage indication in Appendix C. (There is no additional Voltage measurement with an DMM necessary. PTB checked the stability of the power supply and lamp.)

8. Results

All lamps and power supply units were circulated among the project partners in a round-robin scheme between January and March 2026. The measurement sequence was slightly adjusted compared to the original plan as follows:

8.1. Ageing effects

All LIS-A² lamps were operated for approximately 30 hours each during the intercomparison. The pilot laboratory calibrated the lamps before and after their circulation among the partners, as well as once during the comparison, in order to quantify ageing effects. Variations due to lamp ageing and differing operating conditions were corrected based on the accumulated burning time and the voltage changes of the lamps, which were continuously recorded using a notebook.

Figure 14 Relative change in spectral irradiance $E(\lambda)$ per hour operating time.

The function shown in the figure above was utilized for the correction of all subsequent evaluations. The burning times at the individual partner laboratories are known.

8.2. Electrical properties

Figure 15 Voltage of LIS-A² LED#1 circuit 1 equipped with 5 CIE-E LEDs.

Figure 16 Voltage of LIS-A² LED#1 circuit 2 equipped with 5 UV LEDs.

Figure 17 Voltage of LIS-A² LED#1 circuit 3 equipped with 5 CIE-E LEDs.

The voltage traces shown above clearly demonstrate that the heat sink temperature control performed excellently over the three-month period. The LEDs maintained highly stable operating conditions throughout and exhibited very good reproducibility. The behavior of the other LIS-A lamps is very similar and shows no significant deviations, so their detailed representation can be omitted.

8.3. Results of PTB (Pilot)

The PTB served as the pilot laboratory and coordinated the intercomparison. Measurements were conducted using a scanning double monochromator (Instrument Systems Spectro 320D) and an array spectroradiometer (Instrument Systems CAS 140CTS).

The Spectro 320D offers high spectral resolution and precise wavelength calibration, ideal for detailed scanning of emission spectra, while the CAS 140CTS provides fast, simultaneous multi-channel detection across a wide spectral range with low stray light and high dynamic range.

Figure 18 Spectral irradiances of the different lamps measured at PTB. The LIS-A² lamps were measured in 500 mm distance. The halogen lamp was measured in 300 mm and in 500 mm distance. The expanded uncertainties are included, but barely visible.

In order to ensure a sufficient high irradiance on the entrance optics of the spectroradiometer, two different distances to the lamps were selected for the intercomparison. The halogen lamp was measured at a distance of 300 mm in order to maintain an adequate signal-to-noise ratio below 450 nm. The measurements of all LED lamps were conducted at a distance of 500 mm. In order to facilitate optimal visualisation, the diagram also demonstrates the spectral irradiance of the halogen lamp at 500 mm, thereby illustrating that the LEDs generate considerably higher irradiance levels below 600 nm.

8.4. Results of ISFH

Figure 19 Spectral irradiances of the different lamps measured at ISFH. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

The used spectroradiometer does not cover the entire visible spectral range from 360 nm to 830 nm, but only from 380 nm to 780 nm. The pronounced overshoot at the spectral edges represents an unresolved and implausible phenomenon, which is why the following analysis restricts the spectral range to 440–770 nm.

Figure 20 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #1 measured at ISFH and PTB. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 21 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #2 measured at ISFH and PTB. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 22 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #3 measured at ISFH and PTB. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 23 The relative deviations of ISFH from the pilot laboratory are shown for LIS-A² lamp #1. The dashed line represents the deviation of the participant's absolute values. The solid line shows the deviation of the irradiance values after correction using the halogen incandescent lamp deviation.

Figure 24 The relative deviations of ISFH from the pilot laboratory are shown for LIS-A² lamp #2. The dashed line represents the deviation of the participant's absolute values. The solid line shows the deviation of the irradiance values after correction using the halogen incandescent lamp deviation.

Figure 25 The relative deviations of ISFH from the pilot laboratory are shown for LIS-A² lamp #3. The dashed line represents the deviation of the participant's absolute values. The solid line shows the deviation of the irradiance values after correction using the halogen incandescent lamp deviation.

8.5. Results of CSIC

Figure 26 Spectral irradiances of the different lamps measured at CSIC. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

The used spectroradiometer does not cover the entire visible spectral range from 360 nm to 830 nm, but only from 380 nm to 780 nm. The pronounced overshoot at the spectral edges represents an unresolved and implausible phenomenon, which is why the following analysis restricts the spectral range to 400 nm to 770 nm. This overshoot is an artefact from applying Richardson-Lucy deconvolution to the data, in order to correct errors due to bandpass and stray light.

Figure 27 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #1 measured at CSIC and PTB. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 28 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #2 measured at CSIC and PTB. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 29 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #3 measured at CSIC and PTB. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 30 The relative deviations of CSIC from the pilot laboratory are shown for LIS-A² lamp #1. The dashed line represents the deviation of the participant's absolute values. The solid line shows the deviation of the irradiance values after correction using the halogen incandescent lamp deviation.

Figure 31 The relative deviations of CSIC from the pilot laboratory are shown for LIS-A² lamp #2. The dashed line represents the deviation of the participant's absolute values. The solid line shows the deviation of the irradiance values after correction using the halogen incandescent lamp deviation.

Figure 32 The relative deviations of CSIC from the pilot laboratory are shown for LIS-A² lamp #3. The dashed line represents the deviation of the participant's absolute values. The solid line shows the deviation of the irradiance values after correction using the halogen incandescent lamp deviation.

8.6. Results of Le Cnam

The halogen incandescent lamp PTB-KSL-104 and the three LIS-A2#1, LIS-A2#2, LIS-A2#3 lamps were measured under the measurement conditions required in the technical protocol at Le Cnam between February 9 and February 18, 2026.

The instruments used are a reference incandescent lamp FELGS0916, a double monochromator, PM and Si detectors. PM detector has been mounted in front of the second exit slit of monochromator (double monochromator with a spectral bandwidth of 1 nm). Si detector has been mounted to first exit slit (single monochromator with a spectral bandwidth of 2 nm). The Figure 33 shows a description of Le Cnam measurement facility.

Figure 33 Description of Le Cnam measurement bench.

The lamp measurement configurations are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Measurement steps according to wavelength ranges.

Lamp	Wavelength (nm)	Measurement step (nm)	Detector
KSL104	360-830	5	PM and Si
	360 - 490 and 680 - 730	1	PM
LIS-A ²	680 - 730	2	Si
	490 – 680 and 730 - 830	5	PM and Si

Figure 34 Spectral irradiances of the different lamps measured at Le Cnam. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 35 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #1 measured at Le Cnam and PTB. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 36 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #2 measured at Le Cnam and PTB. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 37 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #3 measured at Le Cnam and PTB. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 38 The relative deviations of Le Cnam from the pilot laboratory are shown for LIS-A² lamp #1. The dashed line represents the deviation of the participant's absolute values. The solid line shows the deviation of the irradiance values after correction using the halogen incandescent lamp deviation.

Figure 39 The relative deviations of Le Cnam from the pilot laboratory are shown for LIS-A² lamp #2. The dashed line represents the deviation of the participant's absolute values. The solid line shows the deviation of the irradiance values after correction using the halogen incandescent lamp deviation.

Figure 40 The relative deviations of Le Cnam from the pilot laboratory are shown for LIS-A² lamp #3. The dashed line represents the deviation of the participant's absolute values. The solid line shows the deviation of the irradiance values after correction using the halogen incandescent lamp deviation.

8.7. Results of GGO

Figure 41 Spectral irradiances of the different lamps measured at GGO. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 42 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #1 measured at GGO and PTB. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 43 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #2 measured at GGO and PTB. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 44 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #3 measured at GGO and PTB. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 45 The relative deviations of GGO from the pilot laboratory are shown for LIS-A² lamp #1. The dashed line represents the deviation of the participant's absolute values. The solid line shows the deviation of the irradiance values after correction using the halogen incandescent lamp deviation.

Figure 46 The relative deviations of GGO from the pilot laboratory are shown for LIS-A² lamp #2. The dashed line represents the deviation of the participant's absolute values. The solid line shows the deviation of the irradiance values after correction using the halogen incandescent lamp deviation.

Figure 47 The relative deviations of GGO from the pilot laboratory are shown for LIS-A² lamp #3. The dashed line represents the deviation of the participant's absolute values. The solid line shows the deviation of the irradiance values after correction using the halogen incandescent lamp deviation.

8.8. Results of AALTO

Figure 48 Spectral irradiances of the different lamps measured at AALTO. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

The used spectroradiometer does not cover the entire visible spectral range from 360 nm to 830 nm, but only from 380 nm to 780 nm. The pronounced overshoot at the spectral edges represents an unresolved and implausible phenomenon, which is why the following analysis restricts the spectral range to 440–770 nm.

Figure 49 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #1 measured at AALTO and PTB. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 50 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #2 measured at AALTO and PTB. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 51 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #3 measured at AALTO and PTB. The expanded uncertainties are included, but are sometimes only barely visible.

Figure 52 The relative deviations of AALTO from the pilot laboratory are shown for LIS-A² lamp #1. The dashed line represents the deviation of the participant's absolute values. The solid line shows the deviation of the irradiance values after correction using the halogen incandescent lamp deviation.

Figure 53 The relative deviations of AALTO from the pilot laboratory are shown for LIS-A² lamp #2. The dashed line represents the deviation of the participant's absolute values. The solid line shows the deviation of the irradiance values after correction using the halogen incandescent lamp deviation.

Figure 54 The relative deviations of AALTO from the pilot laboratory are shown for LIS-A² lamp #3. The dashed line represents the deviation of the participant's absolute values. The solid line shows the deviation of the irradiance values after correction using the halogen incandescent lamp deviation.

8.9. Overview of results of LIS-A² LED#1

Figure 55 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #1 measured by all participating laboratories are shown without correction using the halogen incandescent lamp. Measurement uncertainties are not included here to avoid clutter; they are provided in the preceding chapters.

Figure 56 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #1 measured by all participating laboratories are shown with correction using the halogen incandescent lamp. Measurement uncertainties are not included here to avoid clutter; they are provided in the preceding chapters.

8.10. Overview of results of LIS-A² LED#2

Figure 57 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #2 measured by all participating laboratories are shown without correction using the halogen incandescent lamp. Measurement uncertainties are not included here to avoid clutter; they are provided in the preceding chapters.

Figure 58 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #2 measured by all participating laboratories are shown with correction using the halogen incandescent lamp. Measurement uncertainties are not included here to avoid clutter; they are provided in the preceding chapters.

8.11. Overview of results of LIS-A² LED#3

Figure 59 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #3 measured by all participating laboratories are shown without correction using the halogen incandescent lamp. Measurement uncertainties are not included here to avoid clutter; they are provided in the preceding chapters.

Figure 60 Spectral irradiances of the LIS-A² lamp #3 measured by all participating laboratories are shown with correction using the halogen incandescent lamp. Measurement uncertainties are not included here to avoid clutter; they are provided in the preceding chapters.

9. Appendix A – Artefact condition upon arrival

From Laboratory (please underline):

PTB ISFH CSIC Aalto Le Cnam GGO PTB

To Laboratory:

PTB ISFH CSIC Aalto Le Cnam GGO PTB

Has the package been opened during transportation (e.g. customs)? Yes / No

If yes, please provide further details:

Is the package damaged in any way? Yes / No

If yes, please provide further details:

Are the contents of the package damaged in any way? Yes / No

If yes, please provide further details:

We confirm the receipt of the lamps and power supplies for the 22IEM05 NEWSTAND interlaboratory comparison.

Date and Name

Please send this document to thorsten.gerloff@ptb.de and saulius.nevas@ptb.de

10. Appendix B – Artefact condition upon departure

Laboratory (please underline):

PTB ISFH CSIC Aalto Le Cnam GGO PTB

Were the artefacts damaged in any way while at your laboratory? Yes / No

If yes, please provide further details:

Were the artefacts altered in any way while at your laboratory? Yes / No

If yes, please provide further details:

Date and Name

Please send this document to thorsten.gerloff@ptb.de and saulius.nevas@ptb.de

11. Appendix C – Table of results

Laboratory (please underline):

PTB	ISFH	CSIC	Aalto	Le Cnam	GGO	PTB
	Description	LIS-A ² LED #1	LIS-A ² LED #2	LIS-A ² LED #3		PTB-KSL-104
	Current Sourceme- ter 1 /A					not applicable
	Current Sourceme- ter 2 /A					not applicable
	Current Sourceme- ter 3 /A					not applicable
	Voltage Sourceme- ter 1 /V					not applicable
	Voltage Sourceme- ter 2 /V					not applicable
	Voltage Sourceme- ter 3 /V					not applicable
	Total operating time /minutes					
	Preliminary result: Spectral irradiance integrated from 360 nm to 830 nm /W m ⁻²					

Date and Name

Please send this document to thorsten.gerloff@ptb.de and saulius.nevas@ptb.de

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22IEM05 NEWSTAND

1 April 2026

A3.1.3 Report on the interlaboratory comparison of the newly developed broadband transfer standard NIR sources

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Contents

Disclaimer	3
1. Introduction and scope	4
2. Type of comparison	4
3. Measurand	4
4. Sources and participants	4
4.1. Monitor spectroradiometer	5
4.2. Reference measurements	5
5. Description of the transfer standard sources	5
5.1. Broadband source RISE-Fiber	5
5.1.1. Design description	5
5.1.2. Specifications	6
5.1.3. Nominal operating conditions	7
5.2. Broadband source RISE-LED	9
5.2.1. Design description	9
5.2.2. Specifications	10
5.2.3. Nominal operating conditions	11
5.3. Broadband source IRIS by METAS	13
5.3.1. Design description	13
5.3.2. Specifications	14
5.3.3. Nominal operating conditions	14
6. Results	16
6.1. Broadband source RISE-Fiber	16
6.1.1. Spectral irradiance	16
6.1.2. Reproducibility	17
6.1.3. Intercomparison	18
6.2. Broadband source RISE-LED	19
6.2.1. Spectral irradiance	19
6.2.2. Reproducibility	20
6.2.3. Intercomparison	21
6.3. Broadband source IRIS	22
6.3.1. Spectral irradiance	22
6.3.2. Reproducibility	23
6.3.3. Intercomparison	24
6.3.4. Long-term reproducibility	25
7. Conclusions	27
Acknowledgments	28

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1. Introduction and scope

This report summarizes the results of the interlaboratory comparison of newly developed broadband transfer standard NIR sources arranged within activity A3.1.3. According to the project protocol, at least one of the broadband transfer standard NIR sources developed in A1.2.3 was to be measured, with the aim of verifying the uncertainties that can be achieved at calibration laboratory level [as low as 0.5 % ($k = 2$)]. Three sources, two developed by RISE and one by METAS were included in the measurements.

2. Type of comparison

The original plan was to circulate the sources among participants. However, during the project, this appeared unfeasible due to the fragility and complexity of the sources. Thus, the sources were brought to PTB Braunschweig, and the participants brought their spectroradiometers there. The measurements were carried out on October 20 to 24, 2025.

3. Measurand

The measurand was spectral irradiance in [$W\ m^{-2}\ nm^{-1}$]. All spectroradiometers were aligned to the same reference distance from the source. These distances were measured in the beginning, and during measurements, set mechanically.

4. Sources and participants

Three NIR sources were measured, RISE-Fiber and RISE-LED developed by RISE, and IRIS developed by METAS. The participants, their instruments participating, and their key characteristics are listed in Table 1. All devices were array spectroradiometers, except PTB-ref, that was used as the reference instrument. Most devices measured large wavelength ranges up to visible and near infrared regions. For RISE-Fiber, results were analyzed in the spectral range from 610 nm to 1250 nm, for RISE-LED from 675 nm to 1250 nm and for IRIS from 550 nm to 1200 nm, where the sources had measurable signal. A more detailed description of the spectroradiometers can be found in "A3.1.4 Report on the measurement intercomparison of the transfer standard array spectroradiometers".

Table 1 Technical specification of the participating array spectroradiometers.

Participant	Spectroradiometer Name	Label	Spectral Range / nm	No. of Pixels	Spectral Band-width / nm	Pixel spacing / nm/pixel	Entrance Optics diameter / mm
PTB	BTS2048-VL-TEC-X	sp23	280 - 1050	2048	1	0.4	10
ISFH	CAS-140D	sp38	300 - 1100	1024x128	3.7	0.8	15
ISFH	CAS-140D	sp38	780 - 1700	512	5.7	2	15
GGO	BTS2048-NIR	sp43	950 - 1700	512	5.5	1.5	10
LNE	Ocean Optics NR	sp46	900 - 1700	512	4	1.6-1.5	11
GGO	BTS2048-VL-TEC-X	sp61	280 - 1050	2048	1	0.4	10
NPL	SVC HR-1024i VNIR	sp76	340 - 1010	512	4	1.3	25
NPL	SVC HR-1024i SWIR	sp89	970 - 1910	256	13	2.18	25
PTB	CAS-140D UV-VIS-NIR	sp77	300 -1100	1024x128	3.7	0.8	15
PTB	BTS2048-NIR	sp98	950 - 1700	512	5.5	1.5	10
PTB	Spectro320D	sp01	190 - 1600	n/a	1 (2)	-	15

4.1. Monitor spectroradiometer

During the measurement campaign, all NIR sources were additionally measured using a monitor spectroradiometer, a CAS-140CT array spectroradiometer with the spectral range from 200 nm to 800 nm and with a spectral bandwidth of 3 nm. This was placed in front of the sources shortly after the start and at the end of each session for comparison purposes, in order to verify stability and reproducibility. Due to its available spectral range, the array spectroradiometer is only partially suitable for monitoring the NIR sources, but it can provide sufficient indication of the reproducibility of the irradiance levels.

4.2. Reference measurements

For reference measurements of the spectral irradiance, a Spectro320D double monochromator-based fast scanning spectroradiometer was used. As a double monochromator system, it provides superior stray light suppression and features a symmetrical nearly triangular bandpass function that is constant throughout the spectral range. The spectral range below 885 nm was measured with 1 nm bandwidth using a photomultiplier tube. In the NIR spectral range, measurements with 2 nm bandwidth were taken from 885 nm to 1600 nm using a thermoelectrically cooled InGaAs detector. The entrance optics for the spectroradiometer is a transmissive diffuser (EOP146) with good cosine correction and medium throughput for the spectral range from 190 nm to 2500 nm. Due to the transmission characteristics of the input optics, relatively high standard deviations were observed, particularly in measurements using the InGaAs detector. This resulted in higher measurement uncertainties in some cases, as well as deviations in comparison measurements.

5. Description of the transfer standard sources

Three broadband prototype sources have been produced within the scope of the project. The *RISE-Fiber* and the *RISE-LED* sources were developed at RISE and the *IRIS* was developed at METAS.

5.1. Broadband source RISE-Fiber

5.1.1. Design description

The RISE-Fiber source is based on high-power LEDs from Thorlabs, each with a drive current in the range between 800 mA and 1000 mA. The LEDs are mounted in heat-sunk encapsulation and prepared for coupling of the radiation into an optical fibre, providing a relatively stable operating condition, see Figure 1.

Figure 1 Commercially available fibre-coupled LED, used for the RISE-Fiber source. Picture from Thorlabs.

In order to combine the radiation from several LEDs a fibre bundle is used, also available from Thorlabs. The fibre bundle uses 7 individual fibres which are combined side-by-side at the output end, see Figure 2.

Figure 2 Commercially available fibre-bundle, used for the RISE-Fiber source. Picture from Thorlabs.

The fibres are connected using standard fibre-optic SMA connectors, which simplifies the use. The output is also a fibre connector, see Figure 3.

Figure 3 Fibre-bundle common output, showing the 7 fibre ends. Picture from Thorlabs.

The radiation is directly available from the connector, or a patch cable could be used to bring the radiation to a more suitable position.

5.1.2. Specifications

The components used to assemble the source are listed in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2 RISE-Fiber source LEDs.

Item	Manufacturer/ Supplier	Center wavelength / nm	Bandwidth (typ.) / nm	Max. drive current / mA	Optical power (in 600 μm fibre) / mW	Electrical power / mW
M780F2	Thorlabs	780 \pm 10	28	800	16	1600
M810F3	Thorlabs	810 \pm 10	30	1000	33	3600
M850F3	Thorlabs	850 \pm 10	30	1000	33	3200
M880F2	Thorlabs	880 \pm 10	50	1000	7.8	1700
M940F3	Thorlabs	940 \pm 10	60	1000	30	3800
M970F3	Thorlabs	970 \pm 10	60	1000	16	1900
M1100F1	Thorlabs	1100 \pm 50	50	1000	10	1800

Table 3 Additional RISE-Fiber source components.

Item	Manufacturer/ Supplier	Data
BF76LS01	Thorlabs	Fanout bundle, 7 fibres (FT600EMT) 600 µm core, low-OH fibre 0.39 NA, 400 nm to 2200 nm SMA connectors 1 m total length
SLC-MA12-U	Mightex	12-channel LED Driver USB computer control 1 mA resolution 1000 mA maximum current

The entire RISE-Fiber source is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Image of the RISE-Fiber source. Inset shows the connector end-face.

5.1.3. Nominal operating conditions

The source is normally driven with the settings according to Table 4.

Table 4 RISE-Fiber source drive settings.

LED	Drive current (% of max)
M780F2	60
M810F3	50
M850F3	50
M880F2	100
M940F3	60
M970F3	100
M1100F1	80

The setting in Table 4 renders the spectral content shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Spectral irradiance of RISE-Fiber source at 10 cm distance from connector end-face.

The spectral content shows the measured irradiance but is limited by the spectrometer sensitivity near 1100 nm. Also, the centre wavelength of the 1100 nm LED is most likely in the range between 1100 nm and 1150 nm.

The uniformity of the source has not been explicitly measured but it is indicated by Figure 6.

Figure 6 RISE-Fiber source irradiance distribution at 10 cm distance from the connector end-face.

The picture shows the illumination on a millimetre-scale paper placed 10 cm from the connector end-face. A usable area of at least 30 mm in diameter is feasible, as indicated by the red circle.

5.2. Broadband source RISE-LED

5.2.1. Design description

The RISE-LED source is based on standard infrared LED components which are commercially available. For RISE-LED, components with an incorporated lens were used. Each component was in either a TO-46 or TO-18 package, see Figure 7.

Figure 7 LED components used for RISE-LED source. Picture from Thorlabs.

The LED components were placed side-by-side using a standard circuit board. They were connected according to their required drive current so that LEDs using the same drive current were connected in series, with a maximum of 5 LEDs in series. In total, 21 LEDs were used in the wavelength range between 780 nm and 1100 nm (centre wavelength).

In order to stabilize the temperature of RISE-LED, a thermally conducting epoxy was used to encapsulate the individual components, as seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Image of the lit source RISE-LED, showing the thermally conducting epoxy (grey).

A heater wire was also added to the epoxy which may be used to regulate the operating temperature to a temperature slightly above the temperature achieved when running the LEDs. A simple temperature controller with an on/off functionality and an embedded NTC resistor was used for this purpose.

5.2.2. Specifications

The components used to assemble the source is listed in Table 5.

Table 5 RISE-LED source components.

Item	Manufacturer/ Supplier	Centre wavelength / nm	Bandwidth (typ.) / nm	Max. drive current / mA	Optical power / mW
LED780L	Thorlabs	780 ±20	25	75	33
LED800L	Thorlabs	800 ±20	30	75	30
LED810L	Thorlabs	810 ±20	30	75	33
LED830L	Thorlabs	830 ±20	32	75	33
LED840L	Thorlabs	840 ±20	35	75	33
LED870L	Thorlabs	870 ±20	25	75	33
LED890L	Thorlabs	890 ±20	44	75	18
LED910L	Thorlabs	910 ±20	44	75	33
LED930L	Thorlabs	930 ±20	60	75	22
365-1579-ND	DigiKey	935	80	100	5
LED940E	Thorlabs	940	50	100	6
TSTS7100-ND	DigiKey	950	30	100	17
LED970L	Thorlabs	970 ±20	46	75	33
EOLD-980-015-1	DigiKey	980 ±20	46	100	23
1125-1415-ND (2x)	DigiKey	1020 ±20	50	100	20
LED1050L	Thorlabs	1050 ±50	50	100	8
1125-1498-ND	DigiKey	1070	74	100	24
LED1070L	Thorlabs	1070 ±20	55	100	8
LED1085L	Thorlabs	1085 ±20	50	100	10
5242-EOLD-1100-015-1-ND	DigiKey	1100 ±20	57	100	24

5.2.3. Nominal operating conditions

The source is normally driven with the settings according to Table 6.

Table 6 RISE-LED source drive settings.

LED	Driver circuit no.	Drive current / mA
LED780L	1	70
LED800L	2	50
LED810L	2	50
LED830L	2	50
LED840L	2	50
LED870L	1	70
LED890L	1	70
LED910L	3	75
LED930L	3	75
365-1579-ND	8	100
LED940E	4	70
TSTS7100-ND	5	20
LED970L	6	50
EOLD-980-015-1	6	50
1125-1415-ND	4	70
LED1050L	4	70
1125-1498-ND	4	70
LED1070L	7	60
LED1085L	7	60
EOLD-1100-015	7	60

The setting in Table 6 renders the spectral content shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Spectral irradiance of RISE-LED source at 30 cm distance from the source circuit board surface.

Due to the much larger source size, it is necessary to use the source at 30 cm distance. The uniformity of the source has not been explicitly measured but it is indicated by Figure 10.

Figure 10 Image of the RISE-LED source irradiance distribution at 30 cm distance from the source surface.

The picture shows the illumination on a millimetre-scale paper placed 30 cm from the source. A usable area of at least 40 mm in diameter is feasible, as indicated by the red circle. The entire RISE-LED source is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 Image of the RISE-LED source. The right picture is taken with an infrared-sensitive camera.

5.3. Broadband source IRIS by METAS

5.3.1. Design description

The InfraRed Irradiance Source (IRIS) is based on a red LED board by Intelligent LED Solutions (ILC-ONA7-RDOR-SC201-WIR200), which consists of seven red OSRAM OSOLON™ SSL 80 LEDs (GA CS8PM1.23), electrically connected in series. Each LED chip is packaged with a silicone lens to reduce the half-value angle to typically less 40°.

The LED board is integrated in an aluminium housing, which hosts phosphors developed and deployed by PhosphorTech Corporation. Two different phosphors, both emitting mainly in the IR-A spectral range, are combined in the housing, but are spatially separated. Three LEDs are used to excite the shorter-wavelength phosphors and four LEDs for the longer-wavelength phosphors. The spatial arrangement is chosen to be symmetric around the centre of the housing for each type of phosphor.

To achieve stable and repeatable operating conditions, the aluminium housing is placed on a thermoelectric cooler (Arroyo Instruments 286-01 TECMount) which cools both, the LED board and the aluminium housing containing the phosphors. A graphite sheet is used between the TEC's thermal plate and the source to ensure high thermal conductivity.

The different components of the source are shown in Figure 12 and a photo of the source in operation is depicted in Figure 13.

Figure 12 Drawing of the IRIS based on seven LEDs and two different phosphors (short- and long-wavelength) emitting in the IR-A spectral range.

Figure 13 Picture of the source.

5.3.2. Specifications

The dimensional drawings of the source mounted on the thermoelectric cooler (TEC) are shown in Figure 14. The phosphors are held inside cylindrical holes of 5 mm diameter inside the aluminium housing and are excited by the LEDs behind them.

Figure 14 Drawing of the IRIS mounted on the cold plate of the TEC (lengths in mm).

5.3.3. Nominal operating conditions

Environment

Conditions with ambient temperature between 20 °C and 30 °C and relative humidity between 30 % and 70 % are recommended.

Thermoelectric cooling

For reproducibility, the TEC should be always operated at the same temperature (25 °C recommended) and large gradients between the TEC and the ambient temperature should be avoided. The linear temperature dependence of the LED's centroid wavelength is approximately $0.14 \text{ nm } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ and the LED's radiant flux changes by approximately $-0.4 \% \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ around the TEC temperature of 25 °C for a fix LED forward current of 700 mA.

Electrical parameters

The seven LEDs must be operated with an external constant current source and should be switched on only when the TEC is active. The forward current range is 150 mA to 1000 mA, however, the source is designed to be operated at 700 mA. At the recommended forward current, the forward voltage drop is expected to be less than 18 V.

Alignment and reference plane

For alignment purposes, the source has a dust protection cap with a cross-hair at its centre. It can be used to align the input optics of the detector by means of a laser. A mirror can be placed on the cap to observe the reflected laser beam. The reference plane for the distance setting is the outer plane of the source's aluminium housing, see Figure 14. Due to the limited output of the source, a measurement distance of 300 mm from the reference plane is recommended.

Spatial homogeneity

Due to the short measurement distance and the relatively large effective area of the source, the spatial homogeneity at the measurement plane is not ideal, see Figure 15. Hence, a correction factor needs to be determined and applied for different input optics diameters, see Table 7.

Figure 15 Homogeneity of the IRIS at a distance of 300 mm, measured with an aperture of $D = 2$ mm.

Detector diameter, D / mm	Homogeneity correction factor, $f_{\text{hom,corr.}}$	Standard uncertainty ($k = 1$)
10	0.994 717	0.000 193
11	0.995 576	0.000 155
12	0.996 537	0.000 115
15	1	0
16	1.001 367	0.000 031
20	1.007 944	0.000 093
25	1.019 005	0.000 103
30	1.033 649	0.000 069

Table 7 Correction factors, $f_{\text{hom,corr.}}$, to account for the non-ideal homogeneity at a measurement distance of 300 mm. As reference, a detector with an input optics diameter of $D = 15$ mm is taken.

Temporal stability

A warm-up time of 48 h should be allowed for the shorter wavelength phosphor to reach a temporal drift of less than 0.01 %/h. Before the first use, the source should be seasoned for at least 1000 h and the output monitored in regular intervals.

6. Results

Description of the analysis carried out and figures summarizing the results of the analysis.

6.1. Broadband source RISE-Fiber

6.1.1. Spectral irradiance

The spectral irradiance is composed of the individual spectra of the different LEDs (Figure 16). This results in a spectral profile with several steep slopes. For direct comparison, the spectrum of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp, measured at a distance of 700 mm, is shown. Its irradiance is approximately a factor of 5 smaller than that of a 1000 W tungsten halogen lamp at the same distance. In the spectral range between 750 nm and 1000 nm, the NIR source has a significantly higher irradiance, although it would still be lower than that of a 1000-watt lamp.

Figure 16 Spectral irradiance of the RISE-Fiber broadband source at 300 mm distance measured by several array spectrometers. The dashed line shows the spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp at 700 mm distance.

6.1.2. Reproducibility

During the comparison, the radiation source was operated on two consecutive days (Day 2 and 3 of the campaign). Figure 17 shows that there were noticeable changes at Day 3 (upper light blue line) compared to Day 2 of the measurement campaign. On Day 2, measurements were also made with the reference spectroradiometer, which therefore serves as the reference day (lower red solid line). However, the spectral range of the monitor spectroradiometer is limited to below 800 nm, so strictly speaking, no conclusions can be drawn about the long-wavelength spectral range. Nevertheless, the correction factors are also used here. Using the correction factors, the reference spectrum is adjusted for each measurement day to enable comparability of the measurements with the array spectroradiometers. For Day 3 a correction factor of 0.9862 was chosen.

Figure 17 Relative spectral change of the RISE-Fiber source at different days as indicated by the monitor spectroradiometer. The dotted lines indicate factor for spectrally independent changes which might be used in longer wavelength regions.

6.1.3. Intercomparison

The deviations between the spectral irradiance values reported by the array spectroradiometers and the results from the reference spectroradiometer are shown in Figure 18. The reference spectrum is also shown for illustrative purposes (right y-axis). The dotted lines represent the combined relative expanded measurement uncertainties for each individual array spectroradiometer and the reference spectroradiometer. For the comparison, the instruments were recalibrated on-site against the 150 W halogen incandescent lamp at a distance of 700 mm, and the corrections for the monitor spectroradiometer were taken into account. Good agreement between the spectroradiometers can be observed across wide spectral ranges. Noticeable deviations occur only in spectral regions with steeper slopes, probably because of missing bandpass correction.

Figure 18 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of several array spectroradiometers with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

6.2. Broadband source RISE-LED

6.2.1. Spectral irradiance

The spectral irradiance is composed of the individual spectra of the different LEDs (Figure 19). This results in a spectral profile with several steep slopes. For direct comparison, the spectrum of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp, measured at a distance of 700 mm, is shown. Its irradiance is approximately a factor of 5 smaller than that of a 1000 W tungsten halogen lamp at the same distance. In the spectral range between 750 nm and 1100 nm, the NIR source has a significantly higher irradiance, although it would still be lower than that of a 1000-watt lamp.

Figure 19 Spectral irradiance of the RISE-LED broadband source at 300 mm distance measured by several array spectrometers. The dashed line shows the spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp at 700 mm distance.

6.2.2. Reproducibility

During the comparison, the radiation source was operated on two consecutive days (Day 2 and 3 of the campaign). Figure 20 shows that there were noticeable changes at Day 3 (upper light blue line) compared to Day 2 of the measurement campaign. On Day 2, measurements were also made with the reference spectroradiometer, which therefore serves as the reference day (lower red solid line). However, the spectral range of the monitor spectroradiometer is limited to below 800 nm, so strictly speaking, no conclusions can be drawn about the long-wavelength spectral range. Nevertheless, the correction factors are also used here. Using the correction factors, the reference spectrum is adjusted for each measurement day to enable comparability of the measurements with the array spectroradiometers. For Day 3 a correction factor of 0.9786 was chosen.

Figure 20 Relative spectral change of the RISE-LED source at different days as indicated by the monitor spectroradiometer. The dotted lines indicate factor for spectrally independent changes which might be used in longer wavelength regions.

6.2.3. Intercomparison

The deviations between the spectral irradiance values reported by the array spectroradiometers and the results from the reference spectroradiometer are shown in Figure 21. The reference spectrum is also shown for illustrative purposes (right y-axis). The dotted lines represent the combined relative expanded measurement uncertainties for each individual array spectroradiometer and the reference spectroradiometer. For the comparison, the instruments were recalibrated on-site against the 150 W halogen incandescent lamp at a distance of 700 mm, and the corrections for the monitor spectroradiometer were taken into account. Good agreement between the spectroradiometers can be observed across wide spectral ranges. Larger deviations become apparent only in spectral regions with steeper slopes, most likely due to the lack of bandpass correction.

Figure 21 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of several array spectroradiometers with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{\text{comb}}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

6.3. Broadband source IRIS

6.3.1. Spectral irradiance

The spectral irradiance consists of the spectrum of the excitation photodiode, which peaks at 626 nm, and the overlapping spectra generated by the phosphors (Figure 22). For direct comparison, the spectrum of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp, measured at a distance of 700 mm, is shown. Its irradiance is approximately a factor of 5 smaller than that of a 1000 W tungsten halogen lamp at the same distance. The relatively low irradiance from the IRIS, however, proved sufficient to be measured by the array spectroradiometers. Nevertheless, the reference spectrometer could no longer provide measurements with low measurement uncertainty in the spectral range above 1100 nm.

Figure 22 Spectral irradiance of the IRIS broadband source at 300 mm distance measured by several array spectrometers. The dashed line shows the spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp at 700 mm distance.

6.3.2. Reproducibility

During the comparison, the radiation source was operated on three consecutive days. The monitor spectrometer demonstrated good reproducibility. Figure 23 shows that there were hardly any changes compared to Day 2 of the measurement campaign. On Day 2, measurements were also made with the reference spectroradiometer, which therefore serves as the reference day. In the spectral range of the excitation photodiode's peak, slight spectral changes of up to one percent can be observed, which can be corrected. This may be due to slight changes in the thermal conditions for the LEDs. In the phosphor region, no spectral dependence is detectable, so a spectrally independent correction is applied here with a factor of 0.9985 for Day 1 and 1.0001 for Day 3. However, the spectral range of the monitor spectroradiometer is limited to below 800 nm, so strictly speaking, no conclusions can be drawn about the long-wavelength spectral range. Nevertheless, the correction factors are also used here. Using the correction factors, the reference spectrum is adjusted for each measurement day to enable comparability of the measurements with the array spectroradiometers.

Figure 23 Relative spectral change of the IRIS at different days as indicated by the monitor spectroradiometer. The dotted lines indicate the spectrally independent changes in the region of the phosphor.

6.3.3. Intercomparison

The deviations between the spectral irradiance values reported by the array spectroradiometers and the results from the reference spectroradiometer are shown in Figure 24. The reference spectrum is also shown for illustrative purposes (right y-axis). The dotted lines represent the combined relative expanded measurement uncertainties for each individual array spectroradiometer and the reference spectroradiometer. For the comparison, the instruments were recalibrated on-site against the 150 W halogen incandescent lamp at a distance of 700 mm, and the corrections for the monitor spectroradiometer were taken into account. Good agreement between the spectroradiometers can be observed across wide spectral ranges. Larger deviations become apparent only in spectral regions with steeper slopes, which are likely due to insufficient bandpass correction.

Figure 24 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of several array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Above 1000 nm, however, the combined measurement uncertainty increases significantly, and the deviations fluctuate markedly around zero. This is due to the fact that the reference spectroradiometer already has a poor signal-to-noise ratio in this spectral range. Measurements above 1200 nm were therefore no longer possible at all. However, to still allow a comparison of the array spectroradiometers, which measure up to 1600 nm, Figure 25 shows the deviation of individual array spectroradiometers from the sp43 instrument. The measurements with sp43 were performed on the same day as the measurements with the reference spectroradiometer. It is shown that all spectroradiometers agree within the combined measurement uncertainties, with the exception of the range of very low spectral irradiance values above 1350 nm.

Figure 25 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of several array spectroradiometer with respect to spectroradiometer sp43. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by spectroradiometer sp43 (axis to the right).

6.3.4. Long-term reproducibility

Four months after the initial comparison, the spectrum of the IRIS broadband source was measured again. The measurement took place at METAS under nearly identical conditions. The array spectroradiometers used for this measurement are listed in Table 8. The radiation source had been in additional operation for 195 hours by that time.

Table 8 Technical specification of the spectroradiometers for the additional measurements of the IRIS

Participant	Spectroradiometer Name	Label	Spectral Range / nm	No. of Pixels	Spectral Band-width / nm	Pixel spacing / nm/pixel	Entrance Optics diameter / mm
METAS	CAS-140CT-156	VIS-NIR	300 -1100	1024x128	3.7	0.8	16
METAS	CAS-140CT-171H	IR	780 -1700	512	9	2.1	15

Figure 26 shows the deviation of this follow-up measurement from the reference spectroradiometer, and Figure 27 shows the deviation from the sp43 array spectroradiometer. The supplementary measurement agrees very well with the other measurement results. Only in regions with steep slopes in the IRIS spectrum is a greater deviation observed, since no bandwidth correction was applied. The result demonstrates that a reproducible spectral irradiance can be achieved with the IRIS broadband radiation source even after transporting to a different measurement location.

Figure 26 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of several array spectroradiometers with respect to the reference spectroradiometer. The measurements by spectrometers VIS-NIR and IR were taken 4 months after the intercomparison. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Figure 27 Relative deviations of the spectral irradiance measurements of several array spectroradiometers with respect to spectroradiometer sp43. The measurements by spectrometer IR were taken 4 months after the intercomparison. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainties $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by spectroradiometer sp43 (axis to the right).

7. Conclusions

The three prototype NIR sources developed within the project were successfully operated and measured during the intercomparison campaign at PTB from October 20 to 24, 2025. Additionally, the IRIS broadband source was transported from PTB back to METAS and measured 4 months later. This measurement agreed well with the measurements at PTB in the regions with sufficient irradiance levels, demonstrating the long-term reproducibility of the source. However, the comparison revealed several drawbacks of the prototype sources which are summarised in the following.

The RISE-Fiber source at 300 mm provides a relatively high peak spectral irradiance, comparable to that of a FEL1000W lamp at 700 mm. However, the spectral range is limited mainly between 760 nm and 980 nm with an additional small emission peak around 1100 nm. Moreover, the spectrum exhibits large gradients due to the individual LED emission peaks which is reflected in larger deviations of the measured spectra from the reference spectrum, especially for sp76. This shows that accurate bandpass correction needs to be applied when measuring this type of sources. In general, from the measurements of the monitor spectroradiometer in the range between 680 nm and 780 nm, it can be seen that the source's output in this range varies up to 1.7 % from one day to another. This behaviour needs to be further investigated to achieve better reproducibility. After correction of this deviation, the measured spectra agree well within their expanded measurement uncertainties of 2 % to 3 % ($k = 2$) between 740 nm and 980 nm (except of sp76). The measurements around the additional emission peak of the source at 1100 nm deviate more and do not fully agree within their expanded uncertainties.

The peak spectral irradiance of the RISE-LED source at 300 mm is roughly half of that of the RISE-Fiber source, but the source covers a larger spectral range, mainly emitting between 770 nm and 1120 nm. The source's variations in output from one day to the other measured by the monitor spectroradiometer in the range between 700 nm and 780 nm lie between 1.6 % and 2.4 %. Unfortunately, due to the limited range of the monitor spectroradiometer, the reproducibility at longer wavelengths could not be quantified. The spectral gradients of this source's output are also large and the deviations between the measurement of sp76 and the reference spectroradiometer exceeds the expanded measurement uncertainty, most probably due to insufficient bandpass correction in the measurement. All other measurements show good agreement within their expanded uncertainties of 2 % to 3 % between 760 nm and 1000 nm. Above 1070 nm the deviations are larger, especially for sp43, sp89 and sp98 (up to ± 10 %). This might originate from a less stable output of the source in this spectral range.

The IRIS broadband source uses red LEDs peaking at 626 nm to excite two different IR phosphors, mainly emitting from 700 nm to 1000 nm and from 1200 nm to 1350 nm. The source's main limitation is the very low spectral irradiance level achieved at an already short distance of 300 mm (max. 2.4 mW/m²/nm). The comparison revealed that for many spectroradiometers, the low irradiance does not provide good enough signal to noise ratio, resulting in increased measurement uncertainties. The reference spectroradiometer could not measure the source with sufficiently low uncertainty above 885 nm. Therefore, sp43 was used as a reference in the range above 1100 nm. Regarding the reproducibility, the monitor spectroradiometer measurements at three different days showed relative changes between 710 nm and 780 nm inside ± 0.2 %. The comparison measurements, including the measurement performed 4 months later at METAS, show good agreement within ± 3 % compared to the reference spectroradiometer between 710 nm and 885 nm. The deviations in this range are well below the expanded measurement uncertainties. Above 885 nm, the reference spectroradiometer is not sensitive enough to measure the IRIS and can therefore not be used as a reference. Between 1200 nm and 1350 nm, the 5 measurements (sp43 used as a reference) agree within ± 3 %, well inside the expanded measurement uncertainties ($k = 2$).

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A3.1.4 Report on the measurement intercomparison of the transfer standard array spectroradiometers

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Contents

Disclaimer	4
1. Introduction	5
1.1. Background and objectives	5
1.2. Scope of the intercomparison	5
2. Organisation of the intercomparison.....	5
3. Description of equipment and artifacts	5
3.1. Participating array spectroradiometers (detector-based standards).....	5
3.2. Monitor spectroradiometers.....	8
3.3. Description of sources	8
3.3.1. KSL102, KSL103, KSL104	8
3.3.2. SolSim.....	9
3.3.3. LIS-A ²	10
3.4. The reference spectroradiometer	11
4. Measurement protocol and conditions.....	11
5. Spectroradiometer measurements, calibration and intercomparisons	12
5.1. sp37.....	13
5.1.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	13
5.1.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements.....	14
5.2. sp69.....	15
5.2.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	15
5.2.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements.....	16
5.3. sp79.....	16
5.3.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	17
5.4. sp61.....	18
5.4.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	18
5.4.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements.....	19
5.5. sp13.....	20
5.5.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration	21
5.5.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements	22
5.6. sp43.....	22
5.6.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	23
5.6.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements.....	24
5.7. sp38.....	25
5.7.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	25
5.7.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements.....	26
5.8. sp46.....	28
5.8.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	28
5.8.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements.....	29
5.9. sp76.....	29
5.9.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	30
5.9.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements.....	31

5.10.	sp89.....	32
5.10.1.	Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	32
5.10.2.	Comparison of radiation source measurements.....	33
5.11.	sp51.....	33
5.11.1.	Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	34
5.12.	sp23.....	35
5.12.1.	Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	35
5.12.2.	Comparison of radiation source measurements.....	36
5.13.	sp49.....	37
5.13.1.	Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	38
5.13.2.	Comparison of radiation source measurements.....	39
5.14.	sp98.....	39
5.14.1.	Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	40
5.14.2.	Comparison of radiation source measurements.....	41
5.15.	sp08.....	42
5.15.1.	Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	42
5.15.2.	Comparison of radiation source measurements.....	43
5.16.	sp77.....	43
5.16.1.	Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	43
5.16.2.	Comparison of radiation source measurements.....	44
5.17.	sp55.....	45
5.17.1.	Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	45
5.17.2.	Comparison of radiation source measurements.....	46
5.18.	sp47.....	46
5.18.1.	Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	47
5.18.2.	Comparison of radiation source measurements.....	48
5.19.	sp35.....	49
5.19.1.	Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration.....	49
5.19.2.	Comparison of radiation source measurements.....	50
6.	Conclusions.....	51
7.	References.....	51
	Acknowledgments.....	52

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1. Introduction

This report presents the results of the in-lab comparison campaign arranged as activity A3.1.4. within the framework of the NEWSTAND project.

A3.1.4: PTB will organise an in-lab comparison campaign for at least 5 of the transfer standard array spectroradiometers that were calibrated in A2.2.1-A2.2.7. At least 2 different UV-VIS-NIR sources (available at PTB) will be measured at PTB facilities using the transfer standard spectroradiometers that were calibrated by the NMI participants (PTB, Aalto, CMI, CSIC, IPQ, LNE/Cnam, NPL, TUBITAK, VSL) and the calibration laboratories (GGO, IS, ISFH). A summary report will be written, including information on the uncertainties, which were achieved.

1.1. Background and objectives

The main objective of this interlaboratory comparison is to validate the concept of a detector-based transfer of spectral irradiance unit, i.e. to validate achievable transfer uncertainties by using array spectroradiometers as transfer standard instruments that had been characterised and calibrated by the participating consortium partners representing National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) and calibration laboratories. For practical reasons, the intercomparison was planned to be arranged in the form of a measurement campaign at PTB.

1.2. Scope of the intercomparison

The scope of this intercomparison campaign encompasses the on-site measurement and evaluation of spectral irradiance $E(\lambda)$ across the ultraviolet (UV), visible (Vis), and near-infrared (NIR) spectral regions of a few broadband sources provided by PTB. Each source is measured by characterized and calibrated array spectroradiometers brought by the participating partners to PTB and operated during the measurement campaign.

2. Organisation of the intercomparison

The intercomparison for array spectroradiometers was carried out in the framework of a large-scale measurement intercomparisons campaign organised at PTB during 20. - 24.10.2025. Dedicated measurement setups were prepared before the intercomparison allowing the entrance optics of the participating spectroradiometers to be easily installed for the measurements of pre-aligned sources at a given geometry in a reproducible way. To have a common reference data set, each source measured by the array spectroradiometers was also measured by a scanning double-monochromator spectroradiometer provided by PTB during the intercomparison. Moreover, as the intercomparison was carried out throughout several days period and each spectroradiometer was measuring each source at a different time, the stability of the spectral emissions of each source was monitored by a dedicated spectroradiometer that either was recording the signals continuously or did this before and after the measurements by each participating spectroradiometer. After the campaign each participant processed own individual measurement results to yield spectral irradiances of the measured sources with the associated uncertainties and submitted them to PTB in an agreed data format. PTB as a pilot of the interlaboratory comparison analysed the provided results with the aim to determine agreement between the spectral irradiance measured by the participants and the reference data set.

3. Description of equipment and artifacts

A scanning double-monochromator spectroradiometer, model SPECTRO320D, as a reference instrument, alongside with three monitor spectroradiometers and 15 different array spectroradiometers brought by consortium partners were used to measure different light sources present at PTB. The sources mentioned in this report include Halogen lamps, a small solar simulator SolSim and the broadband white LED source LIS-A².

3.1. Participating array spectroradiometers (detector-based standards)

To evaluate and demonstrate detector-based dissemination methods for spectral irradiance, a diverse ensemble of 15 array spectroradiometers was employed as transfer standards during the measurement intercomparison campaign hosted at PTB.

The participating spectroradiometers represent a wide cross-section of current instrument architectures. To effectively cover the required spectral ranges, the transfer standards varied significantly in their core hardware, incorporating different detector technologies (such as back-thinned CCDs, CMOS, and InGaAs sensors), diverse optical input configurations, and varying spectral resolutions.

Table 1 provides specific technical specifications of the measurement instruments utilized during the campaign.

Table 1 Technical specification of the participating array spectroradiometers

Participant	Spectroradiometer Name	Label	Spectral Range / nm	No. of Pixels	Spectral Bandwidth /nm	Pixel spacing /nm/pixel	Entrance Optics diameter/mm
Aalto	CAS 140D	sp37	219 - 1029	1024x128	3.7	0.8	10
CSIC	Konica Minolta CS-1000	sp69	380 - 780	401	5	0.9	25
GGO	BTS2048-UV	sp79	200 - 430	2048	0.8	0.13	10
GGO	BTS2048-VL-TEC-X	sp61	280 - 1050	2048	1	0.4	10
GGO	BTS2048-UVVISNIR	sp13	200 - 900	2048	2	0.34	10
GGO	BTS2048-NIR	sp43	950 - 1700	512	5.5	1.5	10
ISFH	CAS-140D	sp38	300 - 1100	1024x128	3.7	0.8	15
ISFH	CAS-140D	sp38	780 - 1700	512	5.7	2	15
LNE/Cnam	Ocean Optics NR	sp46	900 - 1700	512	4	1.6-1.5	11
NPL	SVC HR-1024i VNIR	sp76	340 - 1010	512	4	1.3	25
NPL	SVC HR-1024i SWIR	sp89	970 - 1910	256	13	2.18	25
PTB	BTS2048-UV	sp51	200 - 430	2048	0.8	0.13	10
PTB	BTS2048-VL-TEC-X	sp23	280 - 1050	2048	1	0.4	10
PTB	BTS2048-UVVISNIR	sp49	200 - 900	2048	2	0.34	10
PTB	BTS2048-NIR	sp98	950 - 1700	512	5.5	1.5	10
PTB	CAS-140D UV-VIS	sp08	200 - 830	1024x128	3	0.65	15
PTB	CAS-140D UV-VIS-NIR	sp77	300 -1100	1024x128	3.7	0.8	15
TUBITAK	AvaSpec-mini2048L	sp55	350 - 870	2048	2.4	0.29	8
VSL	AvaSpec-VRS2048CL-EVO	sp47	190 - 1100	2048	1.88	0.46	10
VSL	AvaSpec-VRS2048CL-EVO	sp35	190 - 1100	2048	2.44	0.46	10
PTB	Spectro320D	ref	190 - 1600	n/a	1 (2)		15

Table 2 Overview of corrections applied by the participants of the comparison campaign to the participating array spectroradiometers.

Participant	Spectroradiometer Name	Label	Nonlinearity correction	Straylight correction	Bandpass correction	Pixel-wavelength assignment
Aalto	CAS 140D	sp37	no	no	no	manufacturer
CSIC	Konica Minolta CS-1000	sp69	no	no	no	manufacturer
GGO	BTS2048-UV	sp79	yes	SCM + OoR	Woolliams et al.	manufacturer
GGO	BTS2048-VL-TEC-X	sp61	yes	SCM	Woolliams et al.	manufacturer
GGO	BTS2048-UVVISNIR	sp13	yes	SCM + OoR	Woolliams et al.	manufacturer
GGO	BTS2048-NIR	sp43	yes	SCM	Woolliams et al.	manufacturer
ISFH	CAS-140D	sp38	yes	no	no	manufacturer
ISFH	CAS-140D	sp38	yes	no	no	manufacturer
LNE/Cnam	Ocean NR	sp46	yes	no	no	Emission line method
NPL	SVC HR-1024i VNIR	sp76	no	no	Triangular	Emission line method
NPL	SVC HR-1024i SWIR-1	sp89	no	no	Triangular	Emission line method
PTB	BTS2048-UV	sp51	yes	SCM + OoR	Woolliams et al.	Tunable laser and Emission line
PTB	BTS2048-VL-TEC-X	sp23	yes	SCM	Woolliams et al.	Tunable laser and Emission line
PTB	BTS2048-UVVISNIR	sp49	yes	SCM	Woolliams et al.	Tunable laser and Emission line
PTB	BTS2048-NIR	sp98	yes	SCM	Woolliams et al.	Tunable laser and Emission line
PTB	CAS-140D UV-VIS	sp08	yes	SCM	Woolliams et al.	Tunable laser and Emission line
PTB	CAS-140D UV-VIS-NIR	sp77	yes	SCM	Woolliams et al.	Tunable laser and Emission line
TUBITAK	AvaSpec-mini2048L	sp55	no	no	no	Emission line method
VSL	AvaSpec-VRS2048CL-EVO	sp47	yes	SCM	no	Emission line method
VSL	AvaSpec-VRS2048CL-EVO	sp35	yes	SCM	no	Emission line method
PTB	Spectro320D	sp01	no	no	no	Emission line method

Most important array spectroradiometer properties requiring characterizations and respective corrections include spectral stray light, bandpass and nonlinearity. For the spectral stray light correction within the spectral range of the instruments, stray light correction matrix (SCM) by Zong et al. [1] was applied by several partners as marked in Table 2.

The stray light correction was accompanied by long pass filter method for the out-of-range stray light [2] in some cases. For the bandpass functions, some instruments were corrected by using the method by Woolliams et al [3]. A few participants corrected their instruments by using a simplified correction method based on an assumption of a triangular bandpass function. The nonlinearities of most instruments have been characterised and corrected by using polynomial functions applied to dark corrected signals.

To ensure the reliability of array spectroradiometers as transfer standards, comprehensive pre-campaign characterizations were required. Unlike scanning double monochromator, array spectroradiometers rely heavily on various mathematical corrections to achieve low measurement uncertainties. The participating institutes have independently characterised their instruments and applied a series of vital corrections such as linearity correction, stray light correction, bandwidth correction, pixel to wavelength assignment. Table 2 provides a detailed overview of the specific characterizations and correction methodologies implemented by each participant before the campaign. The rigorousness of these corrections and the measurement evaluations is a critical factor, as it will directly influence the suitability of the instruments to be used as transfer standards.

3.2. Monitor spectroradiometers

During the measurement campaign, following array spectroradiometers were used as the continuous monitoring instruments to verify the light sources stability and experimental integrity.

ms1: A gigahertz-Optik BTS2048-UV-S-F spectroradiometer was deployed as a monitor spectroradiometer to track the stability of ultraviolet light sources throughout the measurements. The instrument is equipped with high sensitivity TE-cooled 2048-pixel back-thinned CCD detector and a BiTec sensor, operating over a spectral range of 200 nm to 430 nm. With an optical bandpass of about 0.8 nm and a pixel resolution of 0.13 nm/pixel, it provides accurate and stray-light corrected monitoring of the active light source.

ms2: A CAS140CT-151 spectroradiometer was employed as the monitor spectroradiometer to continuously monitor sources for the visible spectral range such as LIS-A2 for any fluctuations or drift. The instrument covers a spectral range from 360 nm to 830 nm. It is equipped with 1024×128-pixel CCD detector, providing a spectral resolution (FWHM) of 2.2 nm and a data point interval of 0.5 nm.

ms3: A CAS-140CT UV-VIS optimized for UV-VIS spectral range (200 nm-830 nm) was used as a monitor spectroradiometer for sources such as SolSim. It is equipped with 1044×128-pixel TEC-cooled CCD detector, providing a spectral resolution (FWHM) of 2 nm and a data point interval of 0.6 nm. Due to its available spectral range, the array spectroradiometer is only partially suitable for monitoring the broadband sources in the NIR, but it can provide sufficient indication of the reproducibility of the irradiance levels.

3.3. Description of sources

3.3.1. KSL102, KSL103, KSL104

150 W tungsten halogen lamps, designated as KSL102 and KSL103 were utilized as transfer standards. The lamps were operated at varying distances, allowing for significantly different irradiance levels to be achieved Figure 1.

Figure 1 Spectral irradiance of the tungsten halogen standard lamps measured at different distances.

3.3.2. SolSim

This source was used to provide simulated sunlight during the measurements. It is a 500 W xenon short-arc lamp mounted inside an LSH302 housing (Newport Corporation) equipped with integrated cooling and rear reflectors for optimized light collection. The spectral output is directed through an AM 1.5 filter to replicate the natural solar spectrum.

Figure 2 Spectral irradiance of SolSim measured by the reference spectroradiometer. The spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp measured at 300 mm distance is given for comparison (dashed line).

Figure 3 Relative change of SolSim as recorded by the monitor spectroradiometer ms3. The reference was day 2 (middle red line), day 1 is the lower light blue line and day 3 is the upper magenta line.

3.3.3. LIS-A²

This configuration uses 10 Yujiled LEDs to generate a broadband spectrum with equi-energy distribution across the visible range. To achieve a sufficiently high irradiance at a distance of about 700 mm on the entrance optics of a spectroradiometer, ten of these LEDs are driven in series. According to the data sheet, a single LED provides an optical output of approximately 3.6 W when driven at 18 V and 200 mA. In this configuration, the same current flows through all the devices, so the total optical power is approximately the sum of the individual contributions, while the required supply voltage increases accordingly. Operating multiple LEDs in series on a thermally stabilised heatsink helps to maintain uniform operating conditions and reduces current balancing problems, which is important for achieving stable and reproducible irradiance at the measurement plane of the spectroradiometer being used.

Figure 4 Spectral irradiance of LIS-A² measured by the reference spectroradiometer. The spectral irradiance of a 150 W tungsten halogen lamp is given for comparison (dashed line).

Figure 5 Relative change of LIS-A² as recorded by the monitor spectroradiometer ms2. The reference was day 1 (middle black line), also day 1 is the red line and day 2 is the lower ochre line, day 3 is the lower magenta line and the upper light blue line is from an additional measurement at day 4 after the intercomparison.

3.4. The reference spectroradiometer

In this laboratory comparison campaign, the Instrument Systems SPECTRO320D, a double monochromator-based system present at PTB was utilized as a reference spectroradiometer. As a double monochromator system, it provides superior stray light suppression and features a symmetrical nearly triangular bandpass function that is constant throughout the spectral range. This combination of low stray light and high accuracy measurements serve as an excellent baseline for evaluating the performance of the participant array spectroradiometers by comparing the measurements made by the reference spectroradiometer.

The core specifications of used reference spectroradiometer are:

Optical design: Integration of a 320 mm focal length double monochromator with complete data acquisition and evaluation electronics.

Entrance Optics and fibre bundle: Optical probe EOP-146 transmittive diffusor with good cosine correction and medium throughput for the spectral range 190 nm – 2500 nm. OFG-465 mixed fibre bundle 5 m with a bundle diameter of 3 mm.

Spectral Range: Configurable from 190 nm (UV) to 1600 nm (IR) depending on the grating and detector combination. For this intercomparison, the reference spectroradiometer was operated in spectral range from 250 nm to 1600 nm.

UV-VIS range (190 nm to 885 nm): Measurements were performed using 1200 grooves/mm holographic or ruled grating paired with a high-sensitivity Photomultiplier Tube (PMT).

NIR range (885 nm to 1600 nm): The system was automatically switched to a 600 grooves/mm grating and a thermoelectrically cooled InGaAs detector.

Spectral Resolution: For the measurements the spectroradiometer was configured to use 1 nm FWHM bandpass in the UV-VIS range and 2 nm in the NIR range. The spectral scans of the sources were carried out with a sampling interval of 1 nm.

Data acquisition: The recording and evaluation of measurement data using the SpecWin Pro software which provides full control over the SPECTRO 320D hardware.

Calibration: To ensure the absolute accuracy of the reference measurements, the spectroradiometer's spectral irradiance responsivity calibrations were carried out against secondary spectral irradiance standards via measuring a 250 W halogen lamp and a 30 W deuterium lamp at a calibration distance of 300 mm.

Due to the transmission characteristics of the input optics, particularly in measurements below 300 nm, relatively high standard deviations were observed. This resulted in higher measurement uncertainties in some cases, as well as higher noise of deviations in comparison measurements.

4. Measurement protocol and conditions

Dedicated measurement setups were prepared at PTB with different sources in UV-VIS-NIR spectral ranges. These setups enabled the rapid and highly reproducible positioning of each participant's entrance optics

relative to the pre-aligned light sources, guaranteeing a consistent measurement geometry across all evaluations.

To control environmental conditions and prevent ambient stray light, the light sources for the UV, VIS, and NIR spectral regions were installed in separate, dedicated optical laboratories. All the light sources were precisely mounted and aligned relative to the spectroradiometer's entrance optics. To ensure accurate readings, each source was positioned at a specific measurement distance: KSL102 was set at 700 mm and KSL 103 at 449 mm and KSL104 at 300 mm. Additionally, the SolSim source was placed at 787 mm while the LIS-A² was kept at a distance of 450 mm. The light sources were operated and measured one after another. The individual measurement setups were optically isolated from one another using black absorbing walls to preventing background radiation from neighbouring light sources. Once a source was stabilized, the participants within the designated group installed their instruments one after another to record the data. All the spectroradiometer's measurements were strictly accompanied by monitor spectroradiometer measurements to ensure the stability of sources. Apart from this, there was a separate optical set up utilizing the pen-ray lamps to verify the wavelength scale of the arrays spectroradiometers.

Following measurement procedure was used for spectroradiometer's measurements:

1. The entrance optics of the participating spectroradiometer was carefully aligned directly in front of the active light source at the specified measurement distances.
2. The measurement parameters were verified, and an optimal integration time and number of averages was set for the measurements.
3. A sequence of repeated measurements of the light source was executed and recorded.
4. Measurement was taken to quantify the ambient room stray light being scattered into the detector by placing a shader in the optical beam.
5. Additional dark measurements with the internal shutter of spectroradiometer were performed, if required.

In the end, out-of-range measurements were conducted using OoR-filter (an 830 nm long-pass filter), applicable for specific instrument characterization. This allowed participants to quantify and subsequently mathematically correct for internal stray light.

5. Spectroradiometer measurements, calibration and intercomparisons

The participating spectroradiometers with all the applied corrections were used to measure the light sources: KSL102, KSL103, KSL104, LIS-A² and SolSim during the measurement campaign. All these measurements were accompanied by the reference spectroradiometer available at PTB.

Later, each participant processed their measurement results and evaluated the spectral irradiance with measurement uncertainties for the sources used and provided this to PTB. The results were compared with the reference spectroradiometer

Below are the detailed discussions for the results of individual participating spectroradiometer.

The description of the results is divided into two parts. First, in the sections "Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration", the spectral irradiance values of the halogen incandescent lamps reported by the instruments are compared with their nominal calibration values. The first figure in each section shows the deviation from the nominal value. In this case, the comparison is not with the results of the reference spectroradiometer. The deviations can provide an indication as to how well the calibration of the array spectroradiometer fits. To put these deviations into context, the combined measurement uncertainties are shown in each of the diagrams. If the deviations fall within the measurement uncertainties, the results are in agreement. From these measurements, a correction factor $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ can then be calculated to correct the device's measurements accordingly. This is shown in the second figure of each section.

The second sections "Comparison of radiation source measurements" present the deviations of the measured spectral irradiance values for LIS-A² and SolSim from the measurements of the reference spectrometer. Two curves are shown for each case: the deviations of the participant's uncorrected results δE and the deviations $\delta E_{corr,hal}$ of the irradiance values corrected by $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ and the irradiance of the reference spectrometer corrected by the monitor spectroradiometer measurements.

The characteristics of the deviations provide some insight into which aspects of the spectrometer characterization were taken into account.

5.1. sp37

The CAS140D spectroradiometer, manufactured by Instrument Systems, is a UV-VIS-NIR model featuring a back-illuminated CCD detector, covering the spectral range from 219 nm to 1029 nm. The optical configuration includes a 50 μm entrance slit, a built-in shutter for automated dark subtraction and an order-sorting filter. The spectral wavelength scale for the CAS140D was established using the wavelength assignment provided by the manufacturer and the spectrometer is not corrected for linearity, stray light or spectral bandwidth.

Measurements of the KSL104 halogen lamp show a slight spectral-independent offset of about 2 % above 400 nm (Figure 6). Significantly higher deviations occur in the short-wavelength range, which can be attributed to the lack of stray light correction. However, the significantly higher deviations of the KSL103 above 700 nm cannot be explained. It is possible that the stray light measurement of the ambient light was not carried out or corrected properly.

Since the KSL103 lamp was used as a reference for corrections during the measurements on the LIS-A², the deviations above 700 nm continue there as well (Figure 8). Apart from that, there is good agreement within the combined measurement uncertainty. The variation in deviations in the short-wavelength spectral range is attributable to the lack of bandwidth correction at the steep flanks of the LED peaks. Measurements on SolSim were not performed with this spectroradiometer.

5.1.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 6 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 7 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.1.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 8 Relative deviations of the LIS-A² spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.2. sp69

The Konica Minolta CS-1000 portable spectroradiometer covers the visible spectrum from 380 nm to 780 nm. It utilizes a high-resolution photodiode array with 0.9 nm sampling interval and an electrically cooled sensor to enhance signal-to-noise ratios for the measurements. A cosine-corrected diffuser, with a diameter of 25 mm, was used at the entrance for irradiance measurements. The spectroradiometer software used the wavelength assignment provided by the manufacturer and does not provide stray light as well as bandpass corrections.

The discrepancies in the measurements of the halogen lamps show a high offset of -5.5% (Figure 9), which is also reflected in the correction factor (Figure 10). This offset must have occurred during the initial calibration of the spectroradiometer and could possibly be due to an incorrect distance setting. After the appropriate correction using KSL103, the LIS-A² shows good agreement (Figure 11). The variation in deviations in the short-wavelength spectral range is attributable to the lack of bandwidth correction at the steep flanks of the LED peaks. Measurements on SolSim were not performed with this spectroradiometer.

5.2.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 9 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 10 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.2.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 11 Relative deviations of the LIS-A² spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.3. sp79

BTS2048-UV, manufactured by Gigahertz-Optik, used for measurements in ultraviolet region (190 nm – 430 nm). This high-speed TE cooled CCD spectroradiometer features a wide dynamic range, low optical bandpass, and a BiTec sensor. A cosine-corrected diffusor of 10 mm was used for measurements. Independent characterizations and corrections for linearity, stray light, and bandpass were established up to 29 months prior to the campaign. The linearity was validated using two methods: integration time variation and irradiance variation. The instrument was characterized for stray light including the derivation of a stray light correction matrix and use of internal long pass filter to mitigate the out of band spectral stray light. Additionally, wavelength calibration was using a tunable laser system to ensure spectral accuracy across the spectral range. During the measurement campaign, these pre-determined corrections were applied to all acquired spectral data.

Due to the available spectral range up to 430 nm, no measurements were performed with this spectroradiometer on the lamps discussed in this report. Therefore, Figure 12 shows the deviation from the measurement on the KSL104 and the corresponding correction factor is shown in Figure 13. This indicates that the calibration must have shifted over time, likely due to the long interval between the initial calibration and the measurements. The change of approximately 2.5% lies slightly outside the combined measurement uncertainties. Measurements on LIS-A² and SolSim were not performed with this spectroradiometer.

5.3.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 12 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 13 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.4. sp61

BTS2048-VL-TEC-X, manufactured by Gigahertz-Optik, is a thermoelectrically cooled spectroradiometer operating over a spectral range of 280 nm to 1050 nm with a low optical bandpass. It employs Bi-Tec sensor technology which integrates a CCD array with a $V(\lambda)$ -filtered silicon photodiode to enhance dynamic range and linearity. It utilizes a cosine-corrected diffusor of 10 mm for measurements.

Independent characterizations and corrections for linearity, stray light, and bandpass were established up to 16 months prior to the campaign. The linearity was validated using two methods: integration time variation and irradiance variation. The instrument was characterized for stray light including the derivation of a stray light correction matrix and use of internal long pass filter to mitigate the out of band spectral stray light. Additionally, wavelength calibration was using a tunable laser system to ensure spectral accuracy across the spectral range. During the measurement campaign, these pre-determined corrections were applied to all acquired spectral data.

This results in very good agreement with the reference measurements across the entire spectral range, both for the measurements of the halogen lamps (Figure 14) and for the measurement of the LIS-A² (Figure 16). This demonstrates that the comprehensive initial characterization of the instrument remains valid even after a prolonged period of intensive use. Only at the very steep edges of the lines in the NIR do slightly higher deviations occur (Figure 16), which are unavoidable when comparing two spectrometers despite careful bandpass correction.

5.4.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 14 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 15 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.4.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 16 Relative deviations of the LIS-A² spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Figure 17 Relative deviations of the SolSim spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.5. sp13

BTS2048-UVVISNIR (Gigahertz Optik) is a TE-cooled spectroradiometer, operating over a 200 nm to 900 nm spectral range. It is equipped with a 10 mm cosine-corrected diffuser and utilizes a BiTec sensor consists of a CCD array with a $V(\lambda)$ -filtered silicon photodiode. Independent characterizations and corrections for linearity, stray light, and bandpass were established up to 13 months prior to the campaign. The linearity was validated using two methods: integration time variation and irradiance variation. The instrument was characterized for stray light including the derivation of a stray light correction matrix and use of internal long pass filter to mitigate the out of band spectral stray light. Additionally, wavelength calibration was using a tunable laser system to ensure spectral accuracy across the spectral range. During the measurement campaign, these pre-determined corrections were applied to all acquired spectral data.

The deviations in the measurements of the halogen lamps (Figure 18) and the resulting correction factor (Figure 19) indicate that the instrument's initial calibration must have drifted over the long period leading up to the comparison. Nevertheless, there is good agreement between both the uncorrected and corrected spectral irradiance values and the measurement of LIS-A² by the reference spectrometer (Figure 20). The relatively smooth trend of the deviations indicates that the instrument's bandwidth correction also works in the range of the LED peaks. Measurements on SolSim were not performed with this spectroradiometer.

5.5.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 18 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 19 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.5.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 20 Relative deviations of the LIS-A² spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.6. sp43

Operating from 950 nm to 1700 nm with a spectral bandwidth of 5.5 nm, the thermoelectrically cooled BTS2048-NIR (Gigahertz Optik) utilizes a hybrid BiTec sensor (InGaAs array and InGaAs photodiode) and a 10 mm cosine-corrected diffuser for the spectral irradiance measurements. The instrument was comprehensively characterized for linearity, spectral stray light, bandpass, and wavelength assignment. These characterizations were performed approximately 4 months prior to the measurement campaign, and the resulting corrections were applied to the acquired spectral data during the measurement campaign.

When measuring the KSL102, agreement within the measurement uncertainties is observed in the infrared spectral range (Figure 21). However, when measuring the SolSim in the infrared spectral range as shown in Figure 23, higher deviations occur in the region of the source's lines. This demonstrates the limits of bandpass corrections for instruments with a higher bandwidth.

5.6.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 21 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiance. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{\text{comb}}(\lambda)$. The gray dotted line shows the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 22 Correction factor $c_{\text{hal}}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamp.

5.6.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 23 Relative deviations of the SolSim spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.7. sp38

The CAS140D (Instrument Systems) utilizes a dual-sensor configuration (Si and InGaAs) connected by a Y-fiber. The Si-based array covers 300 nm-1100 nm, while the InGaAs extends the range from 780 nm to 1700 nm. The system employs a 400 mm fiber bundle with a coded connector, terminated by a 15 mm cosine-corrected diffuser head.

The instrument was characterized for linearity (determined by irradiance level variation by distance), and no corrections were implemented for spectral stray light and bandpass. Also, wavelength assignment was maintained according to the manufacturer's calibration.

The measurements of the halogen lamps show good agreement over wide spectral ranges (Figure 24), so that the correction factor is largely close to one (Figure 25). In the spectral range below 400 nm, the lack of stray light correction in the measurements becomes apparent, leading to an overestimation of the spectral irradiance. The LIS-A² measurements also show a high degree of agreement within the combined measurement uncertainty (Figure 26). There is also essentially good agreement in the spectral irradiance of the SolSim; however, the lack of bandpass correction leads to significant deviations in the region of the emitter's spectral lines (Figure 27).

5.7.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 24 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 25 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.7.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 26 Relative deviations of the LIS-A² spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Figure 27 Relative deviations of the SolSim spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.8. sp46

The Ocean Optics 'Ocean NR' is a near-infrared spectroradiometer covering the spectral range from 895 nm to 1705 nm with a spectral bandwidth of approximately 4 nm.

This spectroradiometer is characterized for linearity using the double-aperture irradiance variation method prior to the campaign deployment. Wavelength-to-pixel-assignment was established using the emission lines from pen ray lamps. The spectrometer's responsivity was not corrected for atmospheric transmission in the infrared spectral region. Notably, the final data processing after the campaign did not include corrections for spectral stray light or optical bandpass effects.

The measurements of the halogen lamps show good agreement over wide spectral ranges (Figure 28), so that the correction factor is largely close to one (Figure 29). Only in the region of water absorption bands around 1400 nm are naturally higher deviations. The spectrometer was solely used to measure SolSim in the infrared spectral range (Figure 30). There are also good agreements here, though significant deviations are observed in the emitter's lines due to the lack of bandpass correction.

5.8.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 28 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 29 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.8.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 30 Relative deviations of the SolSim spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.9. sp76

The SVC HR-1024i is a “Spectra Vista Corporation” multi-detector array spectrometer, consisting of three detector arrays (VNIR, SWIR-1, and SWIR-2). The entrance optics consist of an integrating sphere with a 25.4 mm diameter aperture and lens attached to a secondary port that collects the diffused light from the integrating sphere directly into the spectroradiometer. The sp76 uses the VNIR detector array, operating over spectral range from 340 nm to 1010 nm.

This spectroradiometer did not use specific corrections for linearity and spectral stray light. The wavelength calibration was established using the emission lines from pen ray lamps. The data processing included the bandpass correction implementation, based on the assumption of a symmetrical (triangular) bandpass with fixed FWHM.

Measurements of the three halogen lamps show a different spectral-dependent deviation above 700 nm (Figure 31). However, the significantly higher deviations of the KSL103 above 700 nm cannot be explained. It is possible that the stray light measurement of the ambient light was not carried out or corrected properly.

Since the KSL103 lamp was used as a reference for corrections during the measurements on the LIS-A², the deviations above 700 nm continue there as well (Figure 33). Apart from that, there is good agreement within the combined measurement uncertainty. The variation in deviations in the short-wavelength spectral range might be an indicator that the bandwidth correction at the steep flanks of the LED peaks was a little imperfect. Measurements on SolSim as shown in Figure 34 were in good agreement over a wide spectral range but showed much higher deviations in the area where the lamp had spectral lines. This also can be attributed to the possibly imperfect bandpass correction.

5.9.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 31 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 32 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.9.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 33 Relative deviations of the LIS-A² spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Figure 34 Relative deviations of the SolSim spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.10. sp89

The sp89 uses the SWIR detector array, operating over spectral range from 970 nm to 1900 nm and measuring with 13 nm bandpass. The entrance optics consist of an integrating sphere with a 25.4 mm diameter aperture and lens attached to a secondary port that collects the diffused light from the integrating sphere directly into the spectroradiometer.

This spectroradiometer did not use specific corrections for linearity and spectral stray light. The wavelength calibration was established using the emission lines from pen ray lamps. The data processing included the bandpass correction implementation, based on the assumption of a symmetrical (triangular) bandpass with fixed FWHM.

When measuring the KSL102, agreement within the measurement uncertainties is observed over a wide range (Figure 35). However, when measuring the SolSim in the infrared spectral range as shown in Figure 37, very significant deviations occur in the region of the source's lines. This indicates a lack of or faulty bandpass correction, which should be performed very carefully given the device's high bandwidth.

5.10.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 35 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 36 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.10.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 37 Relative deviations of the SolSim spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.11. sp51

BTS2048-UV, manufactured by Gigahertz-Optik, used for measurements in ultraviolet region (190 nm – 430 nm). This high-speed TE cooled CCD spectroradiometer features a wide dynamic range, low optical bandpass, and a BiTec sensor. A cosine-corrected diffusor of 10 mm was used for measurements.

A comprehensive characterization was conducted prior to the measurement campaign and during this process, all the manufacturer-provided calibrations and corrections were deactivated. The nonlinearity was characterized through both integration time and irradiance level variations with correction applied using a single polynomial function. Following this, the spectral stray light was mitigated through the application of the stray light correction matrix. To ensure the spectral accuracy, a bandpass correction was implemented using Woolliam’s method, while the pixel-to-wavelength assignment was rigorously determined using tunable laser facility as well as the emission lines from pen-ray lamps.

Due to the available spectral range up to 430 nm, no measurements were performed with this spectroradiometer on the lamps discussed in this report. Therefore, Figure 38 shows the deviation from the measurement on the KSL104 and the corresponding correction factor is shown in Figure 39. Within the combined measurement uncertainties the results are in good agreement. Measurements on LIS-A² and SolSim were not performed with this spectroradiometer.

5.11.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 38 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 39 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.12. sp23

BTS2048-VL-TEC-X, manufactured by Gigahertz-Optik, is a thermoelectrically cooled spectroradiometer operating over a spectral range of 280 nm to 1050 nm with a low optical bandpass. It employs Bi-Tec sensor technology which integrates a CCD array with a $V(\lambda)$ -filtered silicon photodiode to enhance dynamic range and linearity. It utilizes a cosine-corrected diffusor of 10 mm for measurements. The comprehensive characterization of the spectroradiometer encompasses linearity, spectral stray light, optical bandpass, and pixel-to-wavelength assignment wavelength assignment alongside the calibration for spectral irradiance responsivity.

It was completely characterized with all the manufacturer-provided calibrations and corrections turned off. The nonlinearity was characterized through both integration time and irradiance level variations with correction applied using a single polynomial function. Following this, the spectral stray light was mitigated through the application of the stray light correction matrix. To ensure the spectral accuracy, a bandpass correction was implemented using Woolliam's method, while the pixel-to-wavelength assignment was rigorously determined using tunable laser facility as well as the emission lines from pen-ray lamps.

A very good agreement is seen with the reference measurements across the entire spectral range, both for the measurements of the halogen lamps (Figure 40) and for the measurement of the LIS-A² (Figure 42). These results confirm the validity of prior characterizations applied. The measurements of SolSim also show a generally very good agreement (Figure 43), with greater deviations occurring only in the region of the source's sharp spectral lines.

5.12.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 40 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 41 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.12.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 42 Relative deviations of the LIS-A² spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Figure 43 Relative deviations of the SolSim spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.13. sp49

BTS2048-UVVISNIR (Gigahertz Optik) is a TE-cooled spectroradiometer, operating over a 200 nm to 900 nm spectral range. It is equipped with a 10 mm cosine-corrected diffuser and utilizes a BiTec sensor consists of a CCD array with a $V(\lambda)$ -filtered silicon photodiode. It underwent an independent and comprehensive characterization, deactivating the manufacturer provided calibrations and corrections. The evaluation involved linearity, spectral stray light, and bandpass corrections, pixel-to-wavelength assignment alongside the calibration for spectral irradiance responsivity.

The nonlinearity was characterized through both integration time and irradiance level variations with correction applied using a single polynomial function. Following this, the spectral stray light was mitigated through the application of the stray light correction matrix. To ensure the spectral accuracy, a bandpass correction was implemented using Woolliam's method, while the pixel-to-wavelength assignment was rigorously determined using tunable laser facility as well as the emission lines from pen-ray lamps.

A very good agreement is seen with the reference measurements across the entire spectral range, both for the measurements of the halogen lamps (Figure 44) and for the measurement of the LIS-A² (Figure 46). These results confirm the validity of prior characterizations applied. SolSim has not been measured by this spectroradiometer.

5.13.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 44 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 45 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.13.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 46 Relative deviations of the LIS-A² spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{\text{comb}}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.14. sp98

Operating from 950 nm to 1700 nm with a spectral bandwidth of 5.5 nm, the thermoelectrically cooled BTS2048-NIR (Gigahertz Optik) utilizes a hybrid BiTec sensor (InGaAs array and InGaAs photodiode) and a 10 mm cosine-corrected diffuser for the spectral irradiance measurements. It was completely characterized for linearity, stray light, bandpass and pixel-to-wavelength assignment alongside the calibration for spectral irradiance responsivity.

The nonlinearity was characterized through both integration time and irradiance level variations with correction applied using a single polynomial function. Following this, the spectral stray light was mitigated through the application of the stray light correction matrix. To ensure the spectral accuracy, a bandpass correction was implemented using Woolliam's method, while the pixel-to-wavelength assignment was rigorously determined using tunable laser facility as well as the emission lines from pen-ray lamps.

When measuring the KSL102, agreement mainly within the measurement uncertainties is observed in the infrared spectral range (Figure 47). However, when measuring the SolSim in the infrared spectral range as shown in Figure 49, higher deviations occur in the region of the source's lines. This demonstrates the limits of bandpass corrections for instruments with a higher bandwidth.

5.14.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 47 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 48 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.14.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 49 Relative deviations of the SolSim spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.15. sp08

The CAS-140D UV-VIS by Instrument Systems is optimized for measurements in spectral range from 200 nm to 830 nm. It features a cooled, back-thinned CCD area detector, Peltier-cooled to -10°C for enhanced stability. The system features a 3 nm spectral bandwidth and an optical input assembly consisting of an OFG424 Quartz fiber bundle coupled to an EOP-146 cosine diffuser. The spectroradiometer was fully characterized for linearity, stray light, bandpass and pixel-to-wavelength assignment alongside the calibration for spectral irradiance responsivity and corresponding corrections were applied during the data processing.

A very good agreement is seen with the reference measurements across the entire spectral range, both for the measurements of the halogen lamps (Figure 50) and for the measurement of the LIS-A² (Figure 52). These results confirm the validity of prior characterizations applied. SolSim has not been measured by this spectroradiometer.

5.15.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 50 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 51 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.15.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 52 Relative deviations of the LIS-A² spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.16. sp77

Operating from 300 nm to 1100 nm, the Instrument Systems CAS-140D UV-VIS-NIR utilizes a cooled, back-thinned CCD area detector to ensure radiometric stability. The system features a 3.7 nm spectral bandwidth and an optical input assembly consisting of an OFG444 Quartz fiber bundle coupled to an EOP-146 cosine diffuser. The spectroradiometer was fully characterized at and corresponding corrections were applied during the data processing.

A very good agreement is seen with the reference measurements across the entire spectral range, both for the measurements of the halogen lamps (Figure 53) and for the measurement of the LIS-A² (Figure 55). These results confirm the validity of prior characterizations applied. The results for SolSim also show good agreement overall (Figure 56), although the larger deviations in the region of the radiator lines highlight the limits of the bandwidth corrections.

5.16.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 53 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 54 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.16.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 55 Relative deviations of the LIS-A² spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Figure 56 Relative deviations of the SolSim spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{\text{comb}}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.17. sp55

The Avantes, AvaSpec-mini2048L is equipped with a CCD array detector consisting of 2048 pixels. The instrument has a pixel spacing of 0.3 nm per pixel and a spectral bandwidth of 2.4 nm. It is coupled to a multimode fiber (M113L01) with a 400 μm core diameter and an SMA connector. For the pre-characterization, the wavelength assignment provided by the manufacturer was used and no corrections for linearity, spectral stray light, as well as bandpass characterization has been applied.

Above 700 nm, the spectroradiometer shows significant deviations for halogen lamps (Figure 57). This is likely due to an incorrect calibration or dark measurement. This deviation is also evident in the measurement of LIS-A² as shown in Figure 59, although good agreement within the combined measurement uncertainties can be observed below 700 nm. SolSim has not been measured by this spectrometer.

5.17.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 57 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent

the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 58 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.17.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 59 Relative deviations of the LIS-A² spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.18. sp47

The AvaSpec-VRS2048CL-EVO (Avantes), also known as the Varius spectrometer, utilizes a high-resolution 2048-pixel CMOS linear array detector. Optimized for the 190 nm to 1100 nm UV-VIS-NIR range, the system is built on the EVO electronic platform for high-speed data acquisition. For this measurement setup, the spectrometer employs a fiber-coupled integrating sphere as the input optics to ensure uniform light collection.

The characterization of the spectroradiometer included linearity, implementation of SCM to correct for stray light and no bandpass correction. All these characterizations with corresponding corrections were later used for spectral irradiance evaluation.

The measurements of the halogen incandescent lamps each show a similar pattern of deviations, some of which are just within the range of the combined measurement uncertainties (Figure 60). Above 700 nm, there are larger deviations compared to the reference values for KSL103, which is also reflected in the correction factor in Figure 61. The correction has an effect in the long-wavelength spectral range; however, in many areas, the deviations for LIS-A² (Figure 62) and SolSim (Figure 63) lie beyond the combined measurement uncertainties. This has a particular effect on the LED peaks and spectral lines, where no bandpass correction was performed.

5.18.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 60 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 61 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.18.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 62 Relative deviations of the LIS-A² spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{\text{comb}}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Figure 63 Relative deviations of the SolSim spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{\text{comb}}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

5.19. sp35

The AvaSpec-VRS2048CL-EVO (Avantes), also known as the Varius spectrometer, utilizes a high-resolution 2048-pixel CMOS linear array detector. Optimized for the 190 nm to 1100 nm UV-VIS-NIR range, the system is built on the EVO electronic platform for high-speed data acquisition. For this measurement setup, the spectrometer employs a fiber-coupled integrating sphere as the input optics to ensure uniform light collection. The characterization of the spectroradiometer included linearity, implementation of SCM to correct for stray light and not any specific correction for bandpass. All these characterizations with corresponding corrections were later used for spectral irradiance evaluation.

The measurements of the halogen incandescent lamps each show a similar pattern of deviations, some of which are just within the range of the combined measurement uncertainties (Figure 64). Above 700 nm, there are larger deviations compared to the reference values for KSL103, which is also reflected in the correction factor in Figure 65. The correction has an effect in the long-wavelength spectral range; however, in many areas, the deviations for LIS-A² (Figure 66) and SolSim (Figure 67) lie beyond the combined measurement uncertainties. This has a particular effect on the LED peaks and spectral lines, where no bandpass correction was performed.

5.19.1. Measurement of halogen lamps and on-site recalibration

Figure 64 Relative deviations of the tungsten halogen spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectral irradiances. The dotted and dashed lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The gray lines show the spectral irradiances of the standard lamps (axis to the right).

Figure 65 Correction factors $c_{hal}(\lambda)$ for on-site recalibration by the tungsten halogen lamps.

5.19.2. Comparison of radiation source measurements

Figure 66 Relative deviations of the LIS-A² spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

Figure 67 Relative deviations of the SolSim spectral irradiance measurements of the array spectroradiometer with respect to the reference spectroradiometer before (blue line) and after (red line) on-site recalibration. The dotted lines represent the combined expanded measurement uncertainty $U_{comb}(\lambda)$. The solid gray line shows the spectral irradiance as measured by the reference spectroradiometer (axis to the right).

6. Conclusions

The intercomparison campaign hosted at PTB successfully evaluated the performance of 15 array spectroradiometers through the on-site measurement and evaluation of spectral irradiance. All the participating spectroradiometers had undergone independent characterization and calibration by consortium partners prior to the campaign. The performance of these instruments was evaluated using transfer standards provided by PTB (KSL102, KSL103, KSL104) and two other radiation sources, SolSim and LIS-A².

The results of the comparison demonstrate that the characterizations and respective corrections with respect to most important radiometric properties of the instruments, i.e. spectral bandpass functions, stray light, nonlinearities and pixel-to-wavelength assignment, are obligatory as a part of the calibration process. The characterization and calibration data is necessary in order to avoid deviations due to steep slopes, peaks and largely varying spectral irradiance levels of the measured sources and to reach uncertainties as low as 1%.

7. References

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